

The Regulatory Future Of Synthetic Data

**Data synthesis as a resource for scientific research,
innovation, and public policy in the European legal landscape**

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1. Introduction

The evolution of data processing technologies and their increasing incidence in everyday life have posed new and complex challenges for data protection. In this context, the debate on synthetic data, an emerging technology that offers new perspectives for data management, comes into play. In this respect, it is essential to consider synthetic data not only as a technique to guarantee privacy and data security, but also as a means to promote innovation and technological progress, without neglecting the necessary guarantees for the protection of rights and freedoms of individuals. Therefore, the aim of this paper is to analyse the role of synthetic data as an anonymisation tool, exploring the implications from both a technical and a legal point of view. The first chapter of this paper provides a legal/technical overview of the notion of synthetic data, analysing the difference between anonymisation and pseudonymisation on the basis of the requirements of data protection legislation and the provisions and guidelines of the various authorities that have intervened in this matter. In addition, the various synthesis techniques have been analysed according to the state of the art, with a focus on synthesis as an anonymisation technique. The second chapter analyses the current as well as the “future regulatory framework”. This analysis includes the interpretation of existing regulations and the prediction of future trends in data protection, paying particular attention to the role of synthetic data in the context of privacy and data security. In particular, have been examined the provisions contained in Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (hereinafter also referred to as “GDPR”)⁶, in the Data Governance Act⁷, and in the Data Act⁸, assessing how synthesis may be applied or interpreted according to the guidance contained in these regulations. In addition, future perspectives have been explored, such as the inclusion of synthetic data in the AI Act⁹ and the impact of the European Health Data Space¹⁰, as well as the prospect of using synthesis in digital health with respect to the Italian landscape. The last chapter of this paper focuses on the growing importance of synthesising data in contexts other than scientific research, highlighting the need for regulatory updates and evolutionary interpretations to support technological innovation while respecting the rights and freedoms of individuals. Furthermore, it was pointed out that Opinion 05/2014 on anonymisation techniques (WP 216)¹¹ needs a renewed approach by European authorities on the topic, considering synthesis as part of anonymisation techniques, if properly generated¹².

⁶ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation).

⁷ Regulation (EU) 2022/868 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2022 on European data governance and amending Regulation (EU) 2018/1724 (Data Governance Regulation).

⁸ Regulation (EU) 2023/2854 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 December 2023 on harmonised rules on fair access to and use of data and amending Regulation (EU) 2017/2394 and Directive (EU) 2020/1828 (Data Regulation).

⁹ Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act) and amending certain Union legislative acts (of 21 April 2021).

¹⁰ Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the European Health Data Area (of 3 May 2022).

¹¹ Opinion 05/2014 of the Data Protection Working Party (WP 216) on anonymisation techniques, adopted on 10 April 2014, https://ec.europa.eu/justice/article-29/documentation/opinion-recommendation/files/2014/wp216_en.pdf

¹² BEDUSCHI, A. (2024). “Synthetic data protection: Towards a paradigm change in data regulation? *Big Data & Society*”, 11(1). <https://doi.org/10.1177/20539517241231277>.

2. Technical/legal overview of synthetic data

2.1 Definition of synthetic data and possible use

Research and innovation require, by their nature, access to vast amounts of information which, when it concerns natural persons, qualify as personal data. This implies the need to process them in compliance with stringent regulations aimed at safeguarding human freedom and dignity. A commonly adopted approach to balance technological advancement with respect for privacy is the use of anonymised data, which fall outside the scope of data protection legislation.

However, this strategy has not always produced the desired results, mainly due to the “*conceptual gap between legal and mathematical thinking on data privacy*”, as appropriately observed by Aloni Cohen and Kobbi Nissim.¹³ Recently, we have witnessed the emergence of an innovative application of **synthetic data**, which on the one hand balances the privacy needs of data subjects, and on the other hand supports innovation by overcoming the 'obstacles' of the past.

As far as the definition of synthetic data is concerned, a possible classification is proposed by the tech champion Robert Riemann, who states that “*Synthetic data is artificial data that is generated from original data and a model that is trained to reproduce the characteristics and structure of the original data*” and “*this means that synthetic data and original data should deliver very similar results when undergoing the same statistical analysis*”¹⁴. Therefore, such data are the result of synthesising processes that exploit machine learning and artificial intelligence algorithms to create new datasets that 'mimic' the characteristics and statistical relationships of real datasets, but do not contain any direct identifiers. In other words, the synthetic data, if correctly generated, not only faithfully reflect the distribution, trends, and patterns of the original data, but do so in a way that negates any risk of tracing the information back to individuals. This process, does not require the storage of 'primary' data linked to specific individuals and also enables the generation of useful data for statistical and machine learning analyses. Consequently, if on the one hand “*datasets can be created for training machine learning algorithms, thus enabling any model to learn on a broader and more representative information base (thus also avoiding the risks of overfitting) and simulating new or complex situations that are rarely encountered (or impossible to encounter), on the other hand the full protection of the confidentiality of the data subjects to whom the initial data are referred is guaranteed, in compliance with the principle of minimisation*”¹⁵.

On the basis of the approach just described, to synthetic data - if rendered sufficiently anonymous so as to prevent or no longer allow the identification of the data subject (using the wording contained in Recital 26 of the GDPR) - should not be granted data protection guarantees. In particular, what has just been stated “*aims 'downstream', and thus at the*

¹³ COHEN, A., & NISSIM, K., (14 April 2020). Towards formalising the GDPR's notion of singling out, *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 117 (15). 8344-8352.

¹⁴ ROBERT RIEMANN, definition proposed in the TechSonar blog of the European Data Protection Board (EDPB) https://edps.europa.eu/press-publications/publications/techsonar/synthetic-data_en.

¹⁵ LORENZO CRISTOFARO and GABRIELE FRANCO, “*Dati sintetici, la giusta sintesi tra innovazione e privacy: stato dell'arte e scenari*”, Digital Agenda, 26/07/2021.

*output of the synthesising process: if the synthetic data complies - now transformed - with the criteria of an adequate anonymisation upstream, at the state of the art and the available technical and contextual elements, it can escape the protections and fulfilments in the field of personal data protection, due to the absence of re-identifiability and personality. In essence, the challenge here would only be to ensure the continued anonymity of the data, to avoid the application of the GDPR altogether*¹⁶.

To illustrate the mechanism behind a synthetic data generation algorithm, it is appropriate to provide a practical example. Imagine that we have a school yearbook, containing photographs, identification data and quotes (relating to future ambitions) of the students in their final year, as well as information such as grade point average, extracurricular activities, and future college enrolments. From this yearbook, significant statistical data could be extracted, such as drop-out rates or the effect of extracurricular activities on academic performance, filtered by gender or ethnicity.

Now, let us assume that we feed a synthesis algorithm with the data contained in the aforementioned yearbook. We would obtain a new yearbook from a non-existent school, with completely different students, photographs and data that cannot be traced back to the original one. Despite this, interrogating this new artificial database with the same questions asked of the real one, we would obtain statistically identical answers. This is because the synthesising process, if correctly generated, creates a completely new dataset, but one that is statistically equivalent to the original dataset, without the need to use personal data directly.

Therefore, the use of synthetic data is crucial for several reasons. From a privacy perspective, it offers an effective solution for maintaining the anonymity of data subjects, overcoming the limitations of traditional anonymisation, which, in some contexts, may be vulnerable to re-identification techniques in the face of advancing computational and analytical capabilities. Synthetic data, therefore, make it possible to work with rich and informative datasets, minimising the risks associated with compliance with data protection regulations.

From the perspective of innovation and research, synthetic data open up new and promising scenarios¹⁷. For instance, in the health sector, they allow information to be shared for studies and analyses without exposing 'sensitive patient data', accelerating scientific research and the development of new treatments. In the field of artificial intelligence, they facilitate the training of algorithms on vast and varied datasets, improving the quality of predictive models and simulations without running into ethical or legal issues related to the use of personal data¹⁸.

Another significant aspect of synthetic data is their ability to mitigate *biases* in the original data. Through controlled generation techniques, balanced and representative datasets can

¹⁶ LUCA BOLOGNINI, “Un focus su dati sintetici e privacy, con proposte evolutive di soft regulation”, Giuffrè Francis Lefebvre.

¹⁷ VAN BREUGEL, B., & VAN DER SCHAAR, M. (2023). “Beyond privacy: Navigating the opportunities and challenges of synthetic data”. arXiv. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2304.03722>

¹⁸ SAVAGE, N. (2023). “Synthetic data could be better than real data”. Nature. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-023-01445-8>.

be produced, helping to reduce inequalities and improve the fairness of artificial intelligence systems. This is of paramount importance to ensure that emerging technologies are inclusive and do not perpetuate pre-existing discrimination.

In conclusion, synthetic data would represent an advanced solution that harmonises the needs of privacy, data security and innovation. In fact, as indicated by Bellovin, “*Synthetic data offers progress. Though not a silver bullet, the method allows us to put an end to the deidentification–reidentification arms race and focus on what matters: useful, private data. To this extent, we recommend the privacy community accept synthetic data as a valid, next step to the database privacy problem*”¹⁹. In general, synthetic data provide a balance between the need to protect the identity of individuals and the desire to fully exploit the potential of data for research and technological development, being an essential tool in the digital age, with applications ranging from the health sector to technology, from academic research to industry.

2.2 Anonymisation vs Pseudonymisation

The analysis of the concepts of anonymisation and pseudonymisation is crucial in order to frame the perimeter of applicability of the requirements prescribed by the data protection legislation, considering that (in the light of what has been illustrated in the previous paragraph) synthesisation would fall within the first category (i.e. anonymisation).

Going into more detail, anonymisation and pseudonymisation are two fundamental technical measures in the protection of personal data, which fit into the regulatory framework outlined by the GDPR. Both practices aim to reduce the risks associated with the processing of personal data, but differ in methodology and purpose.

In particular, as regards the **notion of anonymisation**, this technique consists of the process of rendering personal data anonymous. Taking into account the reference in Recital 26 of the GDPR, anonymised data are qualified as “*information which does not relate to an identified or identifiable natural person or to personal data rendered anonymous in such a manner that the data subject is not or no longer identifiable*”. Therefore, the concept of ‘anonymity’ is closely linked to the identifiability of the individual. In fact, the aforementioned recital 26 of the GDPR specifies that data can be considered anonymous or sufficiently anonymous if, respectively:

- do not relate to an identified or identifiable natural person, or
- prevent or no longer allow the identification of the persons concerned.

The aforementioned recital makes it clear that to determine whether a natural person is identifiable, it is essential to assess all the resources, such as recognition methods, that the data controller or a third party could logically use to recognise a natural person either directly or indirectly. In assessing the plausibility of using such resources to identify an individual, the same recital 26 of the GDPR goes on to state that a variety of concrete factors must be considered, including the costs and time required to identify the individual,

¹⁹STEVEN M. BELLOVIN, PREETAM K. DUTTA, and NATHAN REITINGER– “*Privacy and synthetic data sets*” (https://law.stanford.edu/wp-content/uploads/2019/01/Bellovin_20190129.pdf).

considering not only the technologies existing at the time of the data processing, but also technological developments.

In the light of the indications contained in the GDPR, it can be concluded that anonymisation consists in transforming personal data in such a way that the data subject is no longer identifiable. This implies an irreversible process whereby, even with the use of all reasonably usable additional information or techniques, it would not be possible to trace the identity of the data subject. This technique implies that anonymised data cease to be considered personal data and, consequently, the GDPR does not apply, as it is not applicable to the processing of anonymous information. Thus, anonymisation would offer strong guarantees in terms of protecting the privacy of individuals, but also implies the loss of specific information useful for certain analyses or processing.

On the other hand, with regard to the **concept of pseudonymisation**²⁰, this technique is expressly defined in Article 4(5) of the GDPR as “*the processing of personal data in such a manner that the personal data can no longer be attributed to a specific data subject without the use of additional information, provided that such additional information is kept separately and is subject to technical and organisational measures to ensure that the personal data are not attributed to an identified or identifiable natural person*” (such as, for example, logical separation and limited access). Therefore, unlike anonymised data, pseudonymised data can be attributed to the individual to whom they relate, but, to do so, it is necessary the use of additional information. Pseudonymisation can therefore be regarded as a useful measure to ensure security in the processing of personal data, which data controllers should adopt in compliance with their obligations under Article 32 of the GDPR; however, it does not exclude the 'personal nature' of the data and therefore does not preclude the application of data protection law.

In this regard, dataset that include personal data may contain direct and indirect identifiers, which make it possible to identify or render identifiable a natural person. A direct identifier is specific information referring to an individual, such as a name or an identification number. An indirect identifier (also referred to as a quasi-identifier) is any piece of information (e.g. a geographical location at a certain time or an opinion on a certain topic) that could be used, by someone who has information about that natural person in order to re-identify that natural person in the dataset. The re-identification probability is thus the probability, within a given dataset, of re-identifying a natural person by transforming pseudonymised data back into personal data through the use of data matching or similar techniques. The usefulness of a dataset can be assessed on the basis of the capacity that the information it contains has with respect to the intended purpose.

Therefore, pseudonymisation is a process by which personal data are processed in such a way that they cannot be attributed to a specific data subject, without the use of additional information. This additional information must be stored separately and subject to appropriate technical and organisational measures to ensure that personal data are not attributed to an identified or identifiable natural person before the pseudonymisation process can be considered completed. Unlike anonymisation, pseudonymisation is

²⁰ LUCA BOLOGNINI, CAMILLA BISTOLFI, “Pseudonymization and impacts of Big (personal/anonymous) Data processing in the transition from the Directive 95/46/EC to the new EU General Data Protection Regulation”, *Computer Law & Security Review*, Volume 33, Issue 2, 2017, Pages 171-181, ISSN 0267-3649, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clsr.2016.11.002>. (<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0267364916302151>).

reversible and, therefore, still requires compliance with the requirements of privacy legislation.

However, it is designed to reduce the risks to the rights and freedoms of data subjects and it helps data controllers to comply with their data protection obligations, while retaining the possibility of analysing pseudonymised data.

In conclusion, both techniques have advantages and limitations. Anonymisation offers a high level of privacy protection by permanently removing the possibility of identification of the data subject, but limits the usefulness of the data for further processing. Pseudonymisation, on the other hand, preserves a certain usefulness of the data by allowing more in-depth analyses, while requiring appropriate security measures to be taken to prevent re-identification of the data subject. The choice between anonymisation and pseudonymisation will depend on the specific objectives of the data processing to be carried out and the applicable data protection requirements.

2.3 The 10 misunderstandings to be avoided when dealing with anonymisation and pseudonymisation (according to AEPD and EDPS)

As analysed in the previous section, anonymisation and pseudonymisation are two fundamental concepts in the context of personal data protection, however, the complexity and technical specificity that characterise these processes have often generated a number of common misunderstandings.

In April 2021, the Spanish *Data Protection Authority (Agencia Española de Protección de Datos - 'AEPD')* and the European *Data Protection Supervisor (EDPS)* jointly published a document analysing the ten most common misunderstandings related to anonymisation²¹. This paper is crucial for understanding the complexities and common misunderstandings surrounding anonymisation and pseudonymisation processes, especially in light of the increasing use of synthetic data as an anonymisation tool.

Below, the ten most common misunderstandings are analysed, and explanations are given for each of them, analysing the potential repercussions with respect to synthesis, in the light of the guidance provided by the aforementioned authorities.

- I. **Misunderstanding: “Pseudonymisation is the same as anonymisation”.** Pseudonymisation should not be equated or confused with anonymisation for the reasons explained in the previous section. In fact, as already analysed, the GDPR defines 'pseudonymisation' as a form of processing of personal data carried out in such a way that they (i.e. the personal data) can no longer be attributed to a data subject without the use of additional information, kept separately and protected by technical and organisational measures to avoid attribution to identified or identifiable natural persons. Therefore, pseudonymised data remain personal data because identification is still possible through the use of additional information. Anonymous data, on the other hand, cannot be associated to specific individuals and, once effectively anonymised, does not fall within the scope of the GDPR.

²¹ Agencia Española Protección Datos & European Data Protection Supervisor: “10 Misunderstandings Related to Anonymisation”, accessible here: https://edps.europa.eu/data-protection/our-work/publications/papers/aepd-edps-joint-paper-10-misunderstandings-related_en.

This misunderstanding underlines the importance of the distinction between pseudonymisation and anonymisation, especially when it comes to synthesis. Indeed, synthetic data can achieve a level of anonymisation by ensuring that the subjects of the data are not identifiable, thus overcoming the limits of pseudonymisation.

II. **Misunderstanding: “Encryption is anonymisation”.** Encryption is not an anonymisation technique, but it can be a powerful pseudonymisation tool. The encryption process employs confidential keys to transform information in a way that reduces the risk of misuse, guaranteeing confidentiality for a defined period. In view of the need to keep the original information accessible, the transformations performed by the encryption algorithms are designed to be reversible, through the decryption process. In this regard, it should be noted that the secret keys used for decryption represent the 'additional information' (as specified in the first misunderstanding), which makes the personal data readable and enables identification. In theory, one could consider the deletion of the encryption key as a means of anonymising the encrypted data; however, this assumption is incorrect. The deletion or unknown status of the decryption key does not guarantee that the encrypted data cannot be decrypted. Several factors influence the confidentiality of encrypted data, particularly in the long term. These factors include the robustness of the encryption algorithm and key, potential information leaks, implementation complexity, the volume of encrypted data and technological advances (e.g. quantum computing).

The clarification that encryption is not an anonymisation technique, but rather a form of pseudonymisation, is also particularly relevant when dealing with synthetic data. In fact, the creation of synthetic data is not based on reversible transformations like encryption, but aims to generate entirely new datasets that retain the statistical properties of the original data, without enabling re-identification.

III. **Misunderstanding: “Anonymisation of data is always possible”.** In reality, it is not always possible to reduce the risk of re-identification below a previously defined threshold while preserving a useful dataset for a specific processing. is a Anonymisation process that seeks to strike an appropriate balance between reducing the risk of re-identification and preserving the usefulness of a dataset for its intended purpose(s). However, in certain contexts or with certain types of data, re-identification risks may not be sufficiently mitigated. This scenario may arise when the total number of potential individuals in the dataset (defined as the 'subject universe') is too small, as in the case of an anonymous dataset containing only 705 members of the European Parliament. Moreover, risks may persist when data categories are highly distinctive among individuals, allowing them to be isolated (e.g. fingerprints of devices accessing a specific website). Another potential case occurs

when datasets include a substantial number of demographic attributes²² or location data²³.

The third misunderstanding thus highlights the challenges of the anonymisation process, which should also be addressed when proceeding with the generation of synthetic data. In particular, it is necessary to carefully consider the usefulness of the dataset versus the risk of re-identification, a balance that synthetic data seek to achieve by creating data that are functional to the purpose but not identifiable.

IV. **Misunderstanding: “Anonymisation is forever”** There are cases in which anonymisation cannot be considered permanent, as there is a risk that some anonymisation processes may be reversed in the future. Circumstances may change over time, and new technical developments and the availability of additional information may undermine previous anonymisation processes. In particular, computing resources and emerging technologies, or innovative applications of existing technologies, available to potential attackers aiming to re-identify an anonymous dataset, evolve over time. For instance, *cloud computing* currently offers effective computing capabilities at previously unimaginable levels and prices. Looking to the future, the advent of quantum computers could redefine what is currently considered 'reasonable means'. Furthermore, the disclosure of additional data over time, such as during a data breach, has the potential to establish links between previously anonymous data and identified individuals. The publication of records spanning many decades and containing highly sensitive information, such as criminal records, could still cause significant harm to individuals or their relatives²⁴. Consequently, the dynamic nature of technological advances means that today's anonymised data could become identifiable in the future, a risk that, although probably to a much lesser extent, could also affect synthetic data. This misunderstanding emphasises the need for continuous risk assessments, even after synthetic data have been generated.

V. **Misunderstanding: “Anonymisation always reduces the probability of re-identification of a dataset to zero”**. The anonymisation process and the way it is implemented will have a direct influence on the likelihood of re-identification risks. A robust anonymisation process seeks to reduce the risk of re-identification to a predefined threshold. This threshold depends on various factors, including the presence of existing mitigation controls (absent in the context of public disclosure), the potential impact on the privacy of individuals in the event of re-identification, the motives and capabilities of an attacker to re-identify data²⁵.

²² ROCHER, L., HENDRICKX, J. M., & DE MONTJOYE, Y. A. (2019). “Estimating the success of re-identifications in incomplete datasets using generative models”. *Nature communications*, 10(1), 1-9, <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41467-019-10933-3>.

²³ XU, F., TU, Z., LI, Y., ZHANG, P., FU, X., & JIN, D. (2017, April). “Trajectory recovery from ash: User privacy is not preserved in aggregated mobility data”. In *Proceedings of the 26th international conference on world wide web* (pp. 1241-1250), <https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/3038912.3052620>.

²⁴ GRAHAM, C. (2012). “Anonymisation: managing data protection risk code of practice”. Information Commissioner's Office <https://ico.org.uk/media/1061/anonymisation-code.pdf>.

²⁵ See in this regard: “External guidance on the implementation of the European Medicines Agency policy on the publication of clinical data for medicinal products for human use” (2016), https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/regulatory-procedural-guideline/external-guidance-implementation-european-medicines-agency-policy-publication-clinical-data_en-o.pdf.

Although achieving 100 per cent anonymisation is the optimal goal from a data protection perspective, in certain cases this may not be feasible, and a residual risk of re-identification must be considered.

Therefore, recognising that no anonymisation process, including the generation of synthetic data, can guarantee absolute anonymisation requires an informed, critical and adaptive approach to risk management and the acceptance of residual risks. In any case, it should be pointed out that synthesis offers a significantly lower identification risk profile than some traditional pseudonymisation methodologies.

- VI. **Misunderstanding: “Anonymisation is a binary concept that cannot be measured”.** In reality, the degree of anonymisation can be analysed and measured. The expression 'anonymous data' should not be interpreted as a 'binary label', suggesting that datasets can be categorised as anonymous or non-anonymous. Instead, each record within a dataset carries a probability of being re-identified, based on its susceptibility to being isolated. A robust anonymisation process systematically assesses the risk of re-identification, emphasising the need to manage and control this risk over time.

With the exception of special cases where data are extensively generalised (e.g. a dataset detailing the annual visitor count of a website per country), the risk of re-identification is never reduced to zero.

This misunderstanding is also crucial in the creation of synthetic data, as this process involves the assessment and quantification of the risk of re-identification, which is far lower in synthetic datasets than in classical pseudonymisation techniques. Furthermore, it would reflect the importance of assessing the degree of anonymisation in synthetic datasets, which is not 'crystallised in time' but should be periodically reassessed²⁶.

- VII. **Misunderstanding: “Anonymisation can be fully automated”.** Automated tools may be used during the anonymisation process, however, given the importance of the context in the overall evaluation process, the intervention of human experts is necessary. In fact, it is necessary to analyse the original dataset, the objectives to be pursued, the techniques to be applied and the risk of re-identification associated with the resulting data.

The identification and elimination of direct identifiers, also known as 'masking', is a crucial aspect of the anonymisation process. However, it is necessary to follow this step with due care, considering other sources of (indirect) identification, typically through quasi-identifiers. While direct identifiers are relatively easy to identify, indirect identifiers may not always be obvious, and failure to detect them may lead to a reversal of the process, resulting in re-identification with implications for individuals' privacy.

Automation can play a crucial role in certain steps of the anonymisation process, such as the elimination of direct identifiers or the consistent application of a generalisation procedure on a variable. However, realising a fully automated process that can

²⁶ BOUDEWIJN, A. T. P., FERRARIS, A. F., PANFILO, D., COCCA, V., ZINUTTI, S., DE SCHEPPER, K., & CHAUVENET, C. R. (2023, November). “Privacy Measurements in Tabular Synthetic Data: State of the Art and Future Research Directions”. In NeurIPS 2023 Workshop on Synthetic Data Generation with Generative AI.

identify quasi-identifiers in various contexts or determine how to optimise the utility of the data, by applying specific techniques to specific variables, seems unlikely. This misunderstanding would also impact the generation of synthetic data, an activity that involves the use of complex algorithms with the involvement of mathematicians and experts, especially to determine and evaluate the appropriateness of the anonymisation process and the usefulness of the data generated.

VIII. **Misunderstanding: “Anonymisation makes data useless”.** A correct anonymisation process keeps data functional for a specific purpose (e.g. for analysis activities). The primary objective of anonymisation is to prevent the identification of natural persons within a dataset. However, the application of anonymisation techniques inevitably imposes restrictions on the potential uses of the resulting dataset. For instance, grouping dates of birth into annual intervals may decrease the risk of re-identification, but may, at the same time, reduce the usefulness of the dataset in certain scenarios. This does not imply that anonymised data become useless; rather, their usefulness depends on their intended purpose and the acceptable risk of re-identification.

Conversely, personal data may not be kept permanently beyond their original purpose, awaiting potential usefulness for other purposes. Anonymisation acts as a solution for some data controllers, allowing them to detach and discard personal data from the dataset while retaining significant utility in the remaining dataset (for instance, anonymising the access *logs* of a website by keeping only the date of access and the page visited, while excluding information on who accessed it).

The principle of 'data minimisation' requires the data controller to assess whether the processing of personal data is necessary for a specific purpose or whether the same purpose can be achieved with anonymised data. In some cases, this assessment may lead to the conclusion that making data anonymous is not in line with the intended purpose. In such cases, the data controller must decide between processing personal data (using techniques such as pseudonymisation) and applying the GDPR, or not processing the data at all.

The creation of synthetic data challenges this misunderstanding by providing datasets that retain the statistical properties of the original data for analysis or algorithm training while ensuring privacy and general data protection compliance.

IX. **Misunderstanding: “Following an anonymisation process that others have successfully used will lead our organisation to equivalent results”.** Anonymisation processes must be adapted to the nature, scope, context, and purposes of the processing, as well as to risks of varying likelihood and severity to the rights and freedoms of natural persons. Anonymisation cannot be universally applied as a standardised recipe, since the context (including the nature, scope, and purposes of data processing) is likely to vary from one situation or organisation to another. The effectiveness of an anonymisation process, as measured by the risk of re-identification, may differ significantly depending on factors such as the limited number of recipients compared to making the data available to the general public. Datasets, existing in different contexts, may present distinct challenges. Crossing these datasets with anonymous data may affect the risk of re-identification. For instance, in Sweden, personal data of taxpayers are publicly accessible, whereas in

Spain they are not. Therefore, even if datasets containing information on Spanish and Swedish citizens undergo an anonymisation process using the same procedure, the associated re-identification risks may vary.

This misunderstanding emphasises that effective anonymisation is strictly dependent on the context in which it is carried out; a principle that is also applicable, *mutatis mutandis*, to the generation of synthetic data. This implies that the effectiveness of anonymisation techniques, including the generation of synthetic data, depends on the specific characteristics of the data and the intended use.

- X. **Misunderstanding: “*There is no risk and no interest in finding out to whom this data refers to*”.** Personal data are valuable in themselves, both for the individuals themselves and for third parties. Re-identifying an individual could have a serious impact on his or her rights and freedoms. Attacks against anonymisation may: i) manifest themselves as deliberate attempts at re-identification, ii) be unintentional re-identification efforts, data breaches or the unauthorised disclosure of data to the public²⁷. The first category involves deliberate efforts to re-identify individuals, while the second includes scenarios where re-identification may occur unintentionally. The possibility that someone re-identifies at least one person in a dataset, driven by curiosity, chance or specific interests (such as scientific research, journalism, or criminal activities) cannot be overlooked²⁸.

Assessing the impact of re-identification on an individual’s private life can be difficult as it inevitably depends on the context and related information. For instance, re-identifying a data subject based on apparently harmless film preferences may lead to inferences about that person’s political inclinations or sexual orientation. However, such personal data belonging to special categories receive 'special protection' (under Article 9 of the GDPR).

This misunderstanding is also particularly relevant for synthetic data, as it emphasises the potential value and risks associated with re-identification (although the latter, as mentioned above, are considerably lower for synthetic data than for traditional pseudonymisation techniques). It emphasises the importance of considering the reasons and consequences of potential re-identification, even in datasets considered anonymous or synthetic.

In conclusion, in the light of the analysis conducted in this section, it is of paramount importance to avoid generating confusion between anonymisation and pseudonymisation, especially with a view to classifying synthesis as an anonymisation technique, in order to ensure effective protection of personal data in compliance with the regulations in force. In fact, synthesising, if done in a rigorous manner, would overcome the limitations imposed by data protection legislation, offering new opportunities for the safe use of data.

²⁷ KHALED EL EMAM and LUK ARBUCKLE, “Anonymizing Health Data” (p. 29-33).

²⁸ KHALED EL EMAM, ELIZABETH JONKER, LUK ARBUCKLE, BRADLEY MALIN, “A Systematic Review of Re-Identification Attacks on Health Data”, 11 December 2011.

2.4 ICO guidelines on anonymisation and pseudonymisation and 'Privacy-Enhancing Technologies' ("PETs")

Also the UK supervisory authority: *Information Commissioner's Office* ("ICO") released its guidelines in 2021 to raise awareness of anonymisation and pseudonymisation. In particular, in May 2021, it published the first part ("*Introduction to anonymisation*"²⁹) and, in October of the same year, the second part ("*How do we ensure anonymisation is effective?*"³⁰) of a draft, submitted for public consultation, entitled: "*Anonymisation, pseudonymisation and privacy enhancing technologies guidance*". In this work, the ICO emphasised that data are the lifeblood of the digital economy, and their sharing is crucial to open up new opportunities. The UK authority emphasised the importance of the benefits that data sharing can bring to organisations, individuals, and society as a whole, but also identified the risks associated with it.

The above-mentioned guidelines complement the ICO's³¹ 'code of practice' on anonymisation, which provides practical advice on how to share personal data in compliance with *data protection* requirements. Focusing on anonymisation, the ICO indicated that it represents an alternative approach to using or sharing data, ensuring that individuals remain unidentifiable. Furthermore, it is pointed out that effective anonymisation techniques provide a '*privacy-friendly*' alternative to sharing personal data. However, it is essential to have a reasonable degree of certainty that the disclosure or sharing of apparently anonymous information will not result in inappropriate disclosure of personal data, e.g. through 're-identification'.

The UK authority also clarifies that whenever anonymisation techniques are applied to personal data, this process falls within the definition of 'processing' as defined by the data protection legislation, implying that such operations substantially alter personal information by rendering them anonymous. This transformation involves several steps, including the aggregation and alteration of data, activities that fall precisely within the scope of the notion of processing. Consequently, it is necessary to fulfil the obligations prescribed by the GDPR to carry out this process, in particular by ensuring the presence of an appropriate legal basis for the processing and clearly defining the purposes of anonymisation. Therefore, although anonymisation is generally considered to be a lawful practice, it is essential to precisely establish the perimeter of anonymisation and to detail the technical and organisational measures taken to achieve it.

According to the ICO, determining the status of information in various circumstances is a key challenge. For example, one may possess information that is clearly personal data, but its *status* when processed by another organisation or by the general public may be unclear. Therefore, similar to the approach taken by the EDPS and the AEPD, analysed in the previous section, the ICO emphasises the need to assess each anonymisation case individually (as a stand-alone scenario). Consequently, although 'absolute' (100 per cent) anonymisation is desirable, it is not always feasible, especially considering the rapid evolution of technology. However, the potential persistence of the risk of re-identification

²⁹ Information Commissioner's Office, "*Introduction to anonymisation*", <https://ico.org.uk/media/about-the-ico/consultations/2619862/anonymisation-intro-and-first-chapter.pdf>.

³⁰ Information Commissioner's Office, "*How do we ensure anonymisation is effective?*", <https://ico.org.uk/media/about-the-ico/documents/4018606/chapter-2-anonymisation-draft.pdf>.

³¹ Information Commissioner's Office, "*Anonymisation: managing data protection risk code of practice*" Anonymisation: managing data protection risk code of practice (ico.org.uk).

does not determine the ineffectiveness of the anonymisation technique; indeed, the UK authority points out that data protection law does not require anonymisation to be completely risk-free. In particular, the specific risk of re-identification must be mitigated so that the possibility of the event occurring is sufficiently remote.

According to the information provided by the ICO in its guidelines, key factors for identifying an individual include, as already indicated by WP29 in its Opinion 05/2014:

1. The identification of a data subject within a *dataset* by the data controller or another entity (**'singling out'**).
2. Linking different *pieces of information* - contained in one or more databases - about the same individual or groups of individuals (**'linkability'**); due to the so-called '*mosaic effect*', individual data do not provide information, but when combined with others, they reveal a meaningful picture.
3. The ability to **infer (so called 'parameter inference')**, guess or predict details about someone based on other available information (**'inferences'**).

Effective anonymisation techniques aim to reduce the potential occurrence of the above-mentioned identifiability conditions, following a risk assessment based on various factors, including the state of the art of technology. The rapid evolution of technology requires such an assessment to be carried out periodically to evaluate whether the measures taken in the initial phase (T₀) remain valid in subsequent phases (T₁, T₂, etc.), or whether new or different measures are needed for the data to remain anonymous.

Another criterion suggested by the ICO to assess the effectiveness of the anonymisation technique adopted, is the so-called '**motivated intruder test**', to assess whether a potential intruder would be able to identify data subjects, whose data have been anonymised, thanks to additional information in his/her possession or otherwise accessible/acquirable. The level of competence of the potential intruder, within the test, should also be parametrised to the type of data involved: the presence, for instance, of financial, biometric, or otherwise highly confidential data, should push towards the use of enhanced security measures.

As regards pseudonymisation, on the other hand, the ICO warns of the risk that, with reference to a specific dataset, the term 'de-identified' refers to personal data that have been processed in such a way that they can no longer be attributed, without further information, to a specific individual. In such a situation, the mistaken belief that the GDPR (or other legislation) does not apply - as reiterated elsewhere, only anonymous data remain outside the scope of the GDPR - could have detrimental consequences for both the data controller and the data subjects. In fact, 'de-identified' data aligns with the definition of pseudonymisation (*ex Art. 4(5) of the GDPR*), differing from anonymised information, because de-identified data have undergone pseudonymisation rather than having been completely anonymised.

The ICO also identified some of the advantages of pseudonymisation, as summarised below:

- a. According to recital 29 of the GDPR, pseudonymisation measures are encouraged not only as a security measure but also as a possible tool for general data analysis;
- b. Pseudonymisation is one of the factors to be considered if a data controller decides to continue processing data for a new purpose compatible with the original purpose;

- c. Pseudonymisation is a key security measure, both at the design stage of processing and during the implementation of any project;
- d. Pseudonymisation techniques may reduce the risk of harm and prejudice to data subjects in the event of a personal data breach and may also facilitate the management of data subjects' rights (some may not apply if the data controller is able to prove the impossibility of identifying data subjects).

Therefore, according to the ICO's guidance, anonymising or pseudonymising personal data can bring significant benefits to a data controller, both in economic and legal terms, provided that compliant measures are implemented in line with best market practices and guidelines provided by data protection authorities.

The ICO guidelines, analysed in this section, are also crucial in the context of synthesisation because they establish clear principles for dealing with data in a privacy-friendly manner, offering guidance on how to correctly apply anonymisation and pseudonymisation techniques. These practices are essential in the generation of synthetic data, a process, as mentioned above, that aims to create data that cannot be directly linked to specific individuals, while retaining its usefulness for analysis and research. By following the ICO's recommendations, organisations can better manage the legal and ethical challenges related to the protection of personal data by ensuring that synthesising is done responsibly and in compliance with applicable regulations.

The issue of synthesisation was addressed by the ICO in its Guide³² dedicated to **privacy-enhancing technologies (PETs)**, stating that through the use of PETs, an organisation can help ensure compliance with the principle of data minimisation and demonstrate data protection by design and by default.

First, the notion of PETs, as described by the ICO, needs to be analysed. PETs are technologies that embody the fundamental principles of data protection by minimising the use of personal data, maximising data security and/or empowering individuals. Data protection legislation does not specifically define PETs, however this concept encompasses various technologies and techniques. The European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA) refers to PETs as: *“software and hardware solutions, i.e. systems encompassing technical processes, methods, or knowledge to achieve specific privacy or data protection functionality or to protect against risks to privacy of an individual or a group of natural persons”*.

In analysing the different types of PETs, the ICO points out that many of them can contribute to data protection compliance, including 'data protection by design and by default', particularly those that:

- reduce the identifiability of the individuals to whom the data are processed, helping to fulfil the principle of data minimisation;
- focus on masking and protecting data, ensuring that security measures are implemented in line with the “state of the art”;
- subdivide or control access to personal data, helping to fulfil the principle of minimisation and ensuring data security, depending on the nature of the processing.

³² ICO - Information Commissioner's Office, *“Privacy - enhancing technologies (PETs)”*, June 2023.

Moreover, in describing PETs that generate or reprocess data - by reducing or eliminating the identifiability of individuals, thereby severing the connection between an individual in the original personal data and the derived data - the ICO specifically mentions differential privacy and synthetic data.

With regard to the relationship between synthetic data and anonymisation, the ICO emphasises that the equivalence between anonymised and synthetic data depends on whether or not it is possible to deduce data of a personal nature from the synthetic data generated by synthesising processes. It is therefore essential to conduct an assessment of the risks of re-identification and inference/attribution linked to synthetic data, focusing, for instance, on the degree of likelihood of re-identification and what information about individuals would be revealed if the identification were successful.

It has also been shown that some synthetic data generation methods are vulnerable to, for instance, *'model inversion'* attacks, which aim at tracing the identification of the individuals to whom the real data refer, or *'membership inference attacks'*, which make it possible to reveal whether particular data (e.g. health-related data) were present in the dataset used to train the AI model.

In general, synthetic data that prevents with a high degree of probability the identification of the data subject should be treated in the same way as data subjected to anonymisation processes and will therefore not be subject to the obligations under data protection legislation.

Regarding the classification of synthesising techniques (based on the state of the art), the Office for National Statistics ('**ONS**'), the largest independent producer of official statistics in the United Kingdom, developed a methodological paper in working paper series number 16 - *'Synthetic data pilot'*³³. This pilot study investigates the demand and requirements for synthetic datasets and explores possible means of producing synthetic data according to specific user needs. It aims to understand how synthetic data can be used to meet analysis and research needs, while ensuring privacy protection and data integrity.

In conclusion, according to the ICO, the use of synthetic data would represent a valid (and, probably, better) alternative to anonymised data, however, some potential criticalities should not be overlooked, arising, in particular the possible *'bias'* of the learning model - i.e. the distortions that may be caused by the use of unrepresentative or poor-quality real data - or, again, the risks of re-identification caused by external attacks (on this point, the ICO has again pointed out that the use of differential privacy with synthetic data may protect a dataset from so called *'linkage' attacks*, however at the expense of the usefulness of the data obtained). In any case, the use of synthetic data as PETs would provide a balance between protecting the privacy of individuals and preserving the utility of the data, supporting organisations in their commitment to data protection compliance.

2.5 EDPS position on synthetic data

The European Data Protection Supervisor ('**EDPS**') is an independent supervisory authority that oversees the application of the GDPR and data protection legislation in

³³ Office for National Statistics' *"Methodology working paper series number 16 - Synthetic data pilot"*, <https://www.ons.gov.uk/methodology/methodologicalpublications/generalmethodology/onsworkingpaperseries/onsmethodologyworkingpaperseriesnumber16syntheticdatapilot>.

general by EU institutions and bodies. The EDPS has shown a keen interest in synthetic data, recognising its potential as a technology for privacy protection.

The EDPS also reiterates that a key element in identifying the material scope of European data protection law is the definition of personal data: indeed, the rules of the GDPR apply to any information concerning an identified or identifiable natural person.

In contrast, data protection principles do not apply to anonymous information, i.e. information that does not relate to an identified or identifiable natural person or to personal data rendered anonymous in such a way that the individual is not or is no longer identifiable. As regards the 'anonymous' nature of synthetic data, the EDPS reiterates that “synthetic data is the product of an artificial process, not related to a real individual, therefore falling outside the scope of the GDPR”³⁴.

According to the EDPS, the availability of large amounts of personal data, the increasing level of interconnection between digital systems, the rising and falling cost of computing power and the ability to draw inferences using Artificial Intelligence (AI) challenge the very concept of anonymous data.

At the same time, Thomas Zerdick, the Head of Technology and Privacy at EDPS, argues that “*there is one technology gaining momentum in the AI context that promises to provide both robust privacy protection and, simultaneously, the possibility to generate useful data when it is not available: data synthesis*”³⁵.

The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (“OECD”) also defines synthetic data as: “*An approach to confidentiality where instead of disseminating real data, synthetic data that have been generated from one or more population models are released*”.

The EDPS describes the concept of synthetic data generation as that process of taking an original data source (dataset) and creating new artificial data with similar statistical properties from it. Maintaining statistical properties means that anyone analysing synthetic data, e.g. a data analyst, should be able to draw the same statistical conclusions from the analysis of a given synthetic dataset as they would if they had the real (original) data at their disposal. Furthermore, it is pointed out that the generation process, also called synthesis, can be performed using different techniques, such as decision trees or deep learning algorithms³⁶. Thus, synthetic data can be classified according to the type of original data: the first type uses real datasets, the second type uses knowledge gathered by analysts, and the third type is a combination of these two. Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) have recently been introduced and are commonly used in the field of image recognition. “*They are generally composed of two neural networks training each other iteratively. The generator network produces synthetic images that the discriminator network tries to identify as such in comparison to real images*”³⁷.

³⁴ WOJCIECH WIEWIÓROWSKI, “Synthetic data: what use cases as privacy enhancing technology”, OPEN Webinar on synthetic data, Synthetic data: what use cases as a privacy enhancing technology? - Wojciech Wiewiórowski | European Data Protection Supervisor (europa.eu).

³⁵ THOMAS ZERDICK, “Is the future of privacy synthetic?”, 14 July 2021, https://www.edps.europa.eu/press-publications/press-news/blog/future-privacy-synthetic_en.

³⁶ NOWOK, B., G.M. RAAB & C. DIBBEN (2016), synthpop: “Bespoke creation of synthetic data in R.”, Journal of Statistical Software, 74:1-26; DOI:10.18637/jss.v074.i11. Retrieved from <https://www.jstatsoft.org/article/view/v074i11>.

³⁷ ROBERT RIEMANN, Tech Champion, Synthetic Data | European Data Protection Supervisor (europa.eu).

In particular, Wojciech Wiewiórowski himself emphasises that no personal data should result from synthesis, otherwise, the risk could be that synthetic data could be a 'privacy mirage', as some academics have called it, because in the end *'there are no privacy gains'*.

A major challenge is the possibility of integrating features from records derived from the original dataset into the synthetic data (known in data protection as outliers). In extreme cases, this could lead to the inference of the data subject. Therefore, and similar to what is done in anonymisation, according to Wojciech Wiewiórowski, *"the process of synthesis should consider a previous preparation of the dataset and, after the model is generated, a privacy assurance assessment should be made to ensure that no data from the dataset comes out in the synthetic data"* ³⁸.

Furthermore, the EDPS identifies potential positive and negative impacts that synthesis may have on personal data protection. As regards the **positive side effects**, synthesis could:

- **Improve privacy in technology:** from a data protection by design approach, this technology could provide, on the basis of a *privacy assurance assessment*, added value for the privacy of individuals whose personal data should not be disclosed.
- **Improve correctness:** synthetic data could help mitigate biases by using correct/exact synthetic datasets to train artificial intelligence models. These datasets are manipulated to have a better 'representativeness of the world' (e.g. without gender or racial discrimination).

On the other hand, on the **negative side**:

- **Output management can be complex:** especially in complex datasets, the best way to ensure that the output is accurate and consistent is to compare the synthetic data with the original data or manually annotated data. However, for this comparison, access to the original data is again required.
- **Difficulties in mapping outliers:** synthetic data can only mimic real-world data; it is not a replica. Therefore, synthetic data may not cover some outliers in the original data. However, for some applications, outliers in the data may be more important than regular data points.
- **The quality of the model depends on the data source:** the quality of synthetic data is strongly correlated with the quality of the original data and the data generation model. Synthetic data may reflect *biases* in the original data. In addition, manipulation of datasets to create fair synthetic datasets may result in inaccurate data.

These aspects underline the importance of a deep evaluation and a careful development when generating and using synthetic data. It is essential to adopt robust methodologies in both the generation of synthetic data and its use, to ensure that the data is not only useful but also free of unintentional *bias*. In addition, when comparing synthetic and original data, it is crucial to maintain high standards of privacy protection to prevent the inadvertent disclosure of 'sensitive' information. These challenges highlight the need for a balance

³⁸ WOJCIECH WIEWIÓROWSKI, *"Synthetic data: what use cases as privacy enhancing technology"*, OPEN Webinar on synthetic data, Synthetic data: what use cases as a privacy enhancing technology? - Wojciech Wiewiórowski | European Data Protection Supervisor (europa.eu).

between the innovative use of synthetic data and ensuring that such use does not compromise the quality of the results, or the privacy of the individuals involved.

In this regard, since in the EDPS's view the use of synthetic data in the context of data protection could prove to be extremely useful, in order to explore this topic in more detail on 17 June 2021, the EDPS held a webinar entitled '*Synthetic data: what use cases as a privacy enhancing technology?*', which was attended by around 170 experts in the field, from both sides of the Atlantic, mostly from industry, but also academics. The focus of the discussion was on the use of synthetic data, instead of real data, as a privacy measure applied in certain sectors (especially in healthcare) and in practical cases, such as artificial intelligence and data science projects or software tests and simulations for technology assessments.

According to EDPS, the challenge that could be overcome through synthesis is to have data that are still useful for their intended purposes, e.g. medical research, because they retain the same statistical properties as the original data, but are no longer those originally collected from individuals.

During the webinar, the various speakers shared their views on how the use of synthesis should be evaluated in relation to 'classical' (original) data anonymisation methods and whether it offers a relevant benefit. Methodologies for calculating how much the use of synthetic data can reduce privacy risks and even commonly accepted privacy risk thresholds were also shared.

The EDPS pointed out that, irrespective of the qualification of synthetic data as personal data, it seems reasonable to argue that, from a '*data protection by design*' approach, this technology provides added value for the privacy of individuals, compared to the disclosure of original data.

In conclusion, as mentioned above, with regard to synthesis, the EDPS suggests conducting a crucial **privacy assurance assessment** to verify that the synthetic data generated are not real personal data. This process assesses the risk of identification of natural persons in the generated synthetic data and how much new information about them could be revealed in the event of successful identification³⁹.

2.6 COURT “Deloitte” judgment: the new scenarios

In its Judgment of 26 April 2023⁴⁰ (hereinafter the “**Judgment**”), the General Court of the CJEU (Eighth Chamber, Extended Composition) (hereinafter also the “**Court**”) expressed its views on the concepts of “pseudonymisation” and “anonymisation” in the context of data processing involving mainly two organisations: one acting as data controller and sender of a set of data, while the other acted as recipient of such data.

The COURT provided an interpretation that appears - for reasons that will be explained below - innovative, triggering a lively debate among practitioners. This debate is undoubtedly fuelled by the crucial importance of these two concepts for the right to data protection.

³⁹ BOUDEWIJN, A. T. P., FERRARIS, A. F., PANFILO, D., COCCA, V., ZINUTTI, S., DE SCHEPPER, K., & CHAUVENET, C. R. (2023, November). “*Privacy Measurements in Tabular Synthetic Data: State of the Art and Future Research Directions*”. In NeurIPS 2023 Workshop on Synthetic Data Generation with Generative AI.

⁴⁰ Judgment of the General Court (Eighth Chamber, Extended Composition), Court of Justice of the European Union, 26 April 2023, https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/IT/TXT/?uri=CELEX:62020TJ0557#t-ECR_62020TJ0557_IT_01-0001. Appeal EDPS v SRB Case C-413/23 P <https://curia.europa.eu/juris/liste.jsf?num=C-413/23&language=en>

As already mentioned, determining whether a piece of data qualifies as personal or not is crucial for the (non)application of the GDPR. Again, it is worth noting that the GDPR does not apply to the processing of anonymised information, whereas it fully applies to the processing of pseudonymised data - with all the implications that entails.

2.6.1 The Case

The case examined by the Court mainly involved the **Single Resolution Board** (“**SRB**”), the European Union's bank resolution authority with the mission to ensure the orderly resolution of distressed banks, and **Deloitte**, which was involved as an independent evaluator contracted by the SRB to conduct evaluations. The evaluations aimed to ascertain whether Banco Popular's shareholders and creditors would have received better treatment had the bank undergone orderly insolvency proceedings.

To summarise, and for the purposes of our analysis, the SRB as part of its institutional activities, collected information relating to shareholders and creditors who participated in the right to be heard procedure (hereinafter also referred to as ‘Data Subjects’). This information included their identification data (necessary for the purposes of the audit) and their personal comments on aspects relevant to the above evaluations. Subsequently, the SRB pseudonymised the comments received and transmitted them to Deloitte without providing any additional information necessary for re-identification. Therefore, the SRB would have remained the only entity capable of linking the comments to the data allowing the identification of the authors.

Moreover, during data collection, the SRB had informed the Data Subjects about the processing of their personal data but had not specified that the comments would be forwarded to Deloitte. This lack of information, according to five complaining data subjects, would have breached the obligation to inform data subjects of the recipients of the personal data processed, as required by the GDPR, which is the reason for the proceedings that led to this judgment.

2.6.2 Key Points of the Judgment

Having established that the submissions and views of the Data Subjects fell within the definition of “personal data” as contained in Article 4(1) of the GDPR, and given that Deloitte did not have access to any information enabling the identification of the authors of the submissions, the Court questioned whether Deloitte should be considered as a “recipient” and, therefore, whether the information transmitted to it constituted “personal data” - that is, information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person.

In particular, for the purposes of our analysis, the Court criticised the decision of the European Data Protection Supervisor (“EDPS”), who was involved in the case following complaints received, to conclude that the submissions sent to Deloitte could only be classified as “personal data” because the SRB, the data controller and a separate entity from Deloitte, had additional information linking these submissions to their authors.

The Court's position can be effectively summarised in paragraphs 96 and 97 of the judgment, which are partially reproduced below:

- **96.** *"Certainly"* - here the General Court agrees with the EDPS, and recalls the so-called Breyer judgment of the Court of Justice of the EU of 19 October 2016, Case -C582/14⁴¹ - *"[...] he fact that the additional information necessary to identify the authors of the comments received during the consultation phase was held not by Deloitte, but by the SRB, does not appear such as to exclude a priori that the information transmitted to Deloitte constituted, for Deloitte, personal data"*.
- **97.** *"However"* - the Court continued, relying on the aforementioned so-called Breyer judgment - *"[...] in order to determine whether the information transmitted to Deloitte constituted personal data, it is necessary to put oneself in Deloitte's position in order to determine whether the information transmitted to it relates to 'identifiable persons'"*.

In line with paragraph 96, the absence of possession of additional information held by the recipient could exclude that the information transmitted (even if held by another entity) constitutes personal data for the recipient.

2.6.3 The Consequences of the Judgment

The judgment thus establishes an important principle in the context of privacy law: the sender's perception of the "personal" nature of the data does not automatically determine the same classification for the recipient. This implies that if the recipient does not consider the data received as personal, the controller has no obligation to inform data subjects about the processing of their data by the receiving entity. This interpretation raises relevant issues that would also impact on the transmission and processing of synthetic data, emphasising the need to assess the nature of the data exchanged between the different entities on a case-by-case basis.

It would seem, therefore, that the court *"introduces a relativistic meaning, even in a subjective sense, to the concepts of anonymisation and pseudonymisation"*⁴², clarifying that:

- it is necessary to consider Deloitte's perspective in determining whether the information submitted to it constitutes personal data, and further
- the fact that the SRB holds additional information is *"[...] not capable of excluding a priori that the information transmitted to Deloitte constituted personal data for the latter"*.

The above does not seem to align perfectly with a literal interpretation of the relevant provisions, for the following reasons.

According to Recital 26 of the GDPR, a provision already analysed above, it seems that the anonymity of data should be assessed in relation to the specific entity involved in a particular stage of processing rather than as a whole. To be clear, if the data processed in the context of an activity could be attributed by any of the different entities involved in the processing to the individual to whom the data relate, then such data should be considered personal data in that specific context. This interpretation is supported by at least two literal elements of

⁴¹ Judgment of the Court of Justice of the European Union (Second Chamber), 19 October 2016, PATRICK BREYER v BUNDESREPUBLIK DEUTSCHLAND, EUR-Lex - 62014CJ0582 - EN - EUR-Lex (europa.eu).

⁴² CAROLA CAPUTO e GIOVANNI FERORELLI, *"Pseudonimizzazione" o "anonimizzazione"? Sui dati, questo è il dilemma (e non solo)*, Agenda Digitale, 12 maggio 2023.

Recital 26 of the GDPR: *"To establish the identifiability of a person, account should be taken of all the means, such as identification, which **either the controller or a third party** may reasonably use to identify that natural person **directly or indirectly.**"* Therefore, the European legislator does not seem concerned about which entity can identify the person; it would be sufficient if at least one of them could do so. Similarly, the methods by which identification is carried out, whether direct or indirect, do not seem to be relevant. Indeed, the use of the term "indirectly" suggests, for instance, cases where the controller is able to identify the person through the processor, and vice versa.

According to this interpretation, as argued by EDPS, for a person to be identifiable from a pseudonymised dataset, it would not matter which entity held the additional information; it would be sufficient that at least one entity held it.

With regard to pseudonymisation, the rules mentioned above do not seem to allow for the possibility that data pseudonymised in one context may be considered anonymous in the same context, depending on the entity processing them. This is evident from the definition of "pseudonymisation" itself, as provided above, which introduces, as a condition for a data processing to be considered pseudonymised, the fact that *"additional information is stored separately and subject to technical and organisational measures to ensure that such personal data are not attributed to an identified or identifiable natural person"*. In other words, the separate storage of additional information and the security measures taken to protect that information (including, of course, limiting access to it) are indispensable elements for a dataset to be considered pseudonymised. It is surprising, therefore, that not making the additional information accessible to the data controller could theoretically be considered as rendering such data anonymous, hence non-personal.

In conclusion, far from venturing into a hasty or overly broad interpretation of specific sections of the judgment it remains imperative to meticulously evaluate the identifiability of the data subjects by the data recipient. In order to classify the data as anonymous from the recipient's point of view, a documented assessment is essential, also considering contractual agreements aimed at minimising the risk of re-identification, including the risk of the recipient becoming aware, in any way, of the additional information necessary precisely for re-identification.

This issue is also crucial for the processing of synthetic data, since the latter are generated to maintain the usefulness of the original data without compromising the identifiability of individuals. The judgment would therefore elaborate a corollary, also applicable to synthetic data, which would require a careful assessment of whether and how synthetic data can be considered as personal data, depending on the identifiability retained in the artificially generated data and the information accessible to the recipient.

Once again, the principle of "accountability" and a risk-based approach will have to guide the data controller in these assessments, emphasising the need for thorough procedures for handling the data transferred.

2.7 State-of-the-art synthesising techniques

In today's environment, marked by the rapid advancement of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML), the emergence of synthetic data represents a significant change, offering new opportunities for innovation in compliance with multiple regulations and

ethical aspects⁴³. Such data, generated through advanced algorithms, provide an effective solution to the challenges of collecting, sharing, and managing data in compliance with current data protection regulations⁴⁴.

By circumventing the risks associated with the use of personal data, synthetic data enables the development and improvement of AI and ML models, advancing research in many fields such as medicine, finance and security. The ability to replicate complex and diverse sets of data allows experts to test hypotheses and propose innovative solutions that would otherwise be impossible due to limitations related to the availability of real data.

Conversely, the use of synthetic data raises significant ethical considerations and challenges the prevention of possible bias or distortion.

The generation of synthetic data requires a careful assessment of inequalities in real-world datasets to ensure that technological development supports principles of equity and social justice⁴⁵. Furthermore, while regulations such as the GDPR provide a regulatory framework for the protection of personal data, the integration of such standards in the context of synthetic data raises new issues⁴⁶. Developers must strike a balance between protecting privacy and optimising the utility of synthetic data, seeking a compromise that respects both privacy and the needs of research and innovation.

Therefore, balancing the imperative for innovation with an unwavering commitment to privacy is the framework within which synthetic data will find its most significant application. Managing these challenges is not just a technological issue, but requires constant dialogue between computer scientists, legislators, ethicists, and civil society to shape a future in which artificial intelligence and machine learning can evolve in harmony with fundamental human rights and the protection of personal data⁴⁷.

In light of the aforementioned considerations, the following analysis provides a comprehensive overview of the state-of-the-art synthetic data generation methods.

2.7.1 Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs)

Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs)⁴⁸, introduced by Ian Goodfellow in 2014, represent an innovative model for generating synthetic data. Generative adversarial networks consist of a dualistic architecture comprising a generator (G) and a discriminator (D). The generator's task is to create data that faithfully mimics the distribution of real data; the discriminator, on the other hand, is dedicated to the comparative analysis of such data with real equivalents, pursuing the identification of their authentic

In the early stages of training, the generated data are clearly distinguishable from the originals; however, through an iterative process of refinement, the generator increases its

⁴³ GANEV, G., XU, K., & DE CRISTOFARO, E. (2022). "Understanding how differentially private generative models spend their privacy budget". arXiv preprint arXiv:2305.10994.

⁴⁴ EL EMAM, K. (2022). "Precaution, ethics and risk: Perspectives on regulating non-identifiable data".

⁴⁵ GANEV, G., XU, K., & DE CRISTOFARO, E. (2022). "Understanding how differentially private generative models spend their privacy budget". arXiv preprint arXiv:2305.10994.

⁴⁶ EL EMAM, K. (2022). "Precaution, ethics and risk: Perspectives on regulating non-identifiable data".

⁴⁷ GRESEK, J. (2023). "Synthetic Data and Medical AI - Where Do We Stand?".

⁴⁸ GOODFELLOW, I., et al. (2014). "Generative adversarial networks". arXiv preprint arXiv:1406.2661.

ability to create outputs indiscernible from the real data. Similarly, the discriminator refines its ability to recognise the subtle differences between generated and real data. This competitive dynamic causes both networks to refine each other through successive iterations, culminating in the generator's ability to effectively circumvent the discriminator, with the goal of producing synthetic data that is indistinguishable from the real thing.

In the art world, GANs have opened up new expressive perspectives, enabling experimentation with distinctive visual styles. Initiatives such as “DeepArt” have manifested the ability of GANs to transfigure photographs into artistic creations⁴⁹ that emulate the techniques of illustrious painters, highlighting the convergence of technology and art.

In the medical sector, GANs find application in the generation of diagnostic images for the training and validation of AI-based diagnostic tools, providing a means to produce extensive image collections suitable for training models without compromising the confidentiality of patient data ⁵⁰.

It is important to note that GANs are not limited to image generation. For example, models such as CTGAN are specifically designed to generate tabular data, and PATE-GAN extends this capability by incorporating differential privacy to ensure that the synthetic data maintains individual privacy^{51,52}. These advances highlight the flexibility of GANs across different data types and applications, further emphasising their importance in the development and improvement of AI.

While GANs open up unprecedented possibilities, they present technical challenges such as mode collapse, which limits the variety of outputs generated, and require computationally intensive and carefully calibrated parameters for effective training. The privacy implications, emerging from the fidelity of synthetic data to their real counterparts, raise confidentiality questions, exposing them to risks such as “inversion attacks”.

However, successful applications of GANs are numerous, as evidenced by “*This Person Does Not Exist*”⁵³, which produces incredibly realistic images of human faces, and by the advancement in artificial intelligence-assisted medical diagnosis systems, which benefit from the generation of synthetic datasets for training, increasing accuracy and reliability.

2.7.2 Autoregressive Models and CNN: technical depth and applications

Autoregressive models, notable for their ability to predict future values from historical data, prove to be a key approach in the analysis of time sequences. These models find extensive application in various fields that require accurate predictions based on past observations, such as weather forecasting, financial market analysis and health monitoring using

⁴⁹ GATYS, L. A., ECKER, A., & BETHGE, M. (2017). “*Neural style transfer: A review*”. arXiv preprint arXiv:1706.08127.

⁵⁰ KISELEVA, A. (2020). “*A review of the application of GANs in medical imaging and healthcare*”. Journal of Healthcare Engineering.

⁵¹ XU, L., SKOULARIDOU, M., CUESTA-INFANTE, A., & VEERAMACHANENI, K. (2019). “*Modeling tabular data using Conditional GAN*”. Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS). Retrieved from <https://arxiv.org/abs/1907.00503>.

⁵² JORDON, J., YOON, J., & VAN DER SCHAAR, M. (2019). “*PATE-GAN: Generating synthetic data with differential privacy guarantees*”. International Conference on Learning Representations (ICLR). Retrieved from <https://openreview.net/pdf?id=S1zk9iRqF7>.

⁵³ <https://www.thispersondoesnotexist.com/>

biometric data ⁵⁴. An example of this approach is the use of Classification and Regression Trees (CART) in Gillian Raab's SynthPop, which, although not neural networks, use autoregressive principles to generate synthetic data based on historical observations⁵⁵.

In addition, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) have improved the processing of visual data. By using convolutional layers that simulate the human visual perception mechanism, CNNs are able to detect distinctive features in images, becoming indispensable tools in applications such as object recognition, medical diagnostic analysis and automated surveillance ⁵⁶.

From a technical point of view, autoregressive models are distinguished by their simplicity and effectiveness in modelling linear relationships between successive data points. However, they may find limitations in the presence of non-linear dynamics or long-term dependencies that elude the most basic models. In these circumstances, variants such as Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) and in particular Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) present themselves as solutions to such limitations, providing models with a long-term memory capacity to deal with elaborate temporal dependencies. More recently, transformers have emerged as a highly effective alternative, using self-attention mechanisms to capture dependencies over long sequences without the sequential processing limitations of RNNs. This makes them suitable for tasks involving extensive temporal relationships⁵⁷.

CNNs, through the use of convolutional filters, process images while maintaining the spatial relationship between pixels, which makes them particularly effective in identifying patterns and textures.

Optimising the effectiveness of these technologies is the subject of research into hybrid models that integrate the capabilities of autoregressive models with those of CNNs. For example, in the field of speech recognition, the combination of autoregressive models with CNNs makes it possible to examine audio sequences over time, capturing both the temporal dynamics and frequency characteristics of the signal ⁵⁸.

2.7.3 Variational autoencoder (VAE) and diffusion models

Variational Autoencoder (VAE) is considered a state-of-the-art technology in the field of deep learning for the generation of synthetic data, with a focus on modelling complex and relational data. This model is characterised by its ability to learn dense latent representations of high-dimensional data, thus enabling the generation of new data that retains the same statistical properties as the original data. A key element of VAE is the use of a loss function that includes a regularisation term called KL divergence, which measures

⁵⁴ GANEV, G., OPRISANU, B., & DE CRISTOFARO, E. (2022). "Robin Hood and Matthew Effects: Differential privacy has disparate impact on synthetic data". In Proceedings of the 39th International Conference on Machine Learning (ICML 2022).

⁵⁵ NOWOK, B., G.M. RAAB & C. DIBBEN (2016), "synthpop: Bespoke creation of synthetic data in R.", Journal of Statistical Software, 74:1-26; DOI:10.18637/jss.v074.i11. Retrieved from <https://www.jstatsoft.org/article/view/v074i11>.

⁵⁶ LECUN, Y., BOTTOU, L., BENGIO, Y., & HAFFNER, P. (1998). "Gradient-based learning applied to document recognition". Proceedings of the IEEE, 86(11), 2278-2324.

⁵⁷ VASWANI, A., SHAZEER, N., PARMAR, N., USZKOREIT, J., JONES, L., GOMEZ, A. N., KAISER, Ł., & POLOSUKHIN, I. (2017). "Attention is All You Need. Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems", 30, 5998-6008. Retrieved from <https://arxiv.org/abs/1706.03762>.

⁵⁸ GRAVES, A., MOHAMED, A., & HINTON, G. (2013). "Speech recognition with deep recurrent neural networks". 2013 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech, and Signal Processing, 6645-6649.

how far the learned distribution in latent space deviates from a predefined distribution, typically Gaussian. This approach forces the model to organise the latent space in a structured and continuous manner, thus facilitating the production of new divergent data. It is important to note that VAEs are not limited to image data; they are also highly effective at generating synthetic data for tables and relational databases, including those with advanced data types. This versatility makes VAEs suitable for a wide range of applications, from image synthesis to the generation of complex tabular data⁵⁹.

Diffusion models, another cutting-edge approach to synthetic data generation, share several similarities with VAEs, particularly in their ability to model complex data distributions. Diffusion models work by defining a forward process that gradually adds noise to the data, transforming it into a noise distribution. A neural network is then trained to approximate the backward process, gradually removing the noise to recover the original data distribution. This iterative process allows diffusion models to produce highly realistic synthetic data that closely resembles real-world data⁶⁰.

VAEs and diffusion models provides robust solutions for generating high fidelity synthetic data. Diffusion models, like VAEs, are effective in capturing complex data structures and have been successfully applied in various domains, including image synthesis and time series predict. Both methods enable the generation of synthetic data that preserve the statistical properties of the original data, while ensuring privacy and compliance with data protection regulations⁶¹.

2.8 Privacy Guarantees

This analysis, which seeks to contextualise synthetic data and their contribution to the modern social fabric, requires a thorough examination of the concept of privacy within a multifaceted legal and operational framework relating to data security. This process involves moving from abstract concepts of confidentiality towards the creation of quantifiable and objectively measurable indicators, requiring in-depth investigation into specific properties and mechanisms.

Translating privacy guarantees in the use of synthetic data into quantifiable parameters becomes essential to establish clear and pragmatic privacy standards. These privacy mechanisms aim to provide a common criterion for assessing the effectiveness of protection measures, which are crucial for quantifying the risk of re-identification or disclosure of sensitive information that could undermine the privacy of individuals.

Before examining the privacy guarantees built into the generation of synthetic data, it is necessary to understand synthetic data in relation to their properties, such as fidelity and usefulness. In essence, the usefulness of a synthetic data depends on its applicability to

⁵⁹ PANFILO, D., BOUDEWIJN, A., SACCANI, S., COSER, A., SVARA, B., CHAUVENET, C. R., MAMI, C. A., & MEDVET, E. (2023). "A deep learning-based pipeline for the generation of synthetic tabular data". IEEE Access.

⁶⁰ HO, J., JAIN, A., & ABBEEL, P. (2020). "Denoising Diffusion Probabilistic Models". Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems, 33, 6840-6851. Retrieved from <https://arxiv.org/abs/2006.11239>.

⁶¹ MAMI, C. A., COSER, A., MEDVET, E., BOUDEWIJN, A. T. P., VOLPE, M., WHITWORTH, M., SVARA, B., SGROI, G., PANFILO, D., & EVAL., S. (2022). "Generating Realistic Synthetic Relational Data through Graph Variational Autoencoders". arXiv:2211.16889v1.

specific purposes or sets of tasks, while fidelity measures how accurately the synthetic data replicates the actual reference data.

Several methods can be used to protect privacy when generating synthetic data, such as ensuring plausible deniability, applying k-anonymity techniques, and implementing controls to prevent overfitting. Differential Privacy represents one of the most discussed and used approaches. This methodology, based on mathematical principles, helps to prevent de-anonymisation by introducing noise ⁶².

However, a critical aspect of Differential Privacy that needs to be considered in this discourse is the allocation of the *privacy budget*, denoted by the Greek letter ϵ (epsilon). This parameter limits the amount of information that can be revealed about an individual, directly affecting the generation of synthetic data and influencing the risk of de-anonymisation. Furthermore, it should be noted that there is a lack of consensus on the ideal choice of the parameter ϵ , as larger values are correlated with a lower level of privacy assurance. Research suggests that a single epsilon value may provide different levels of protection depending on the specific context, and determining an appropriate value is particularly challenging in practical scenarios. This issue is particularly relevant to synthetic data generation, which involves the dissemination of more detailed information than other applications of differential privacy. Unlike differential privacy applied to aggregate statistics - where current guidelines suggest that DP may not provide adequate protection - or to AI classifiers, synthetic data generation involves the release of complete, but synthetic, granular datasets or generative models⁶³. The inadequacy of differential privacy to protect both the privacy and fidelity of synthetic data, regardless of the epsilon value, is further demonstrated by evaluations of synthetic data algorithms⁶⁴.

Below are the advantages and disadvantages of allocating a low and high privacy budget in order to contextualise the application of *differential privacy*.

Low Privacy Budget: Maximum Protection, Limits in Utility

A reduced privacy budget means imposing tight controls on the amount of personal information that can be disclosed⁶⁵. This caution significantly increases privacy protection, but also implies that the synthetic data generated will be less faithful to the originals, with possible distortions limiting its applicability.

Low fidelity: In this scenario, synthetic data differ substantially from real data, resulting in a less accurate representation of specific characteristics. This distance is intended to prevent direct or indirect identification of individuals in the dataset ⁶⁶.

⁶² GU, W. (2021). "Privacy preserving synthetic data generation". Freie Universität Berlin, Berlin, Germany. Retrieved from https://www.mi.fu-berlin.de/inf/groups/ag-idm/theseses/2021_Gu_BSc.pdf.

⁶³ LEE, J., & CLIFTON, C. (2011). "How much is enough? Choosing ϵ for differential privacy". In J. Domingo-Ferrer & I. Tinnirello (Eds.), *Information security* (pp. 325-340). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-24861-0_22

⁶⁴ National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST). (2020). Privacy Collaborative Research Cycle Archive. Retrieved from https://pages.nist.gov/privacy_collaborative_research_cycle/pages/archive.html.

⁶⁵ DWORK, C., MCSHERRY, F., NISSIM, K., & SMITH, A. (2006). "Calibrating noise to sensitivity in private data analysis". In *Proceedings of the Theory of Cryptography Conference (TCC)*, Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol 3876. Springer.

⁶⁶ DWORK, C., & ROTH, A. (2014). "The Algorithmic Foundations of Differential Privacy". *Foundations and Trends® in Theoretical Computer Science*, 9(3-4), 211-407.

Limited utility: The lower fidelity negatively affects the usefulness of the data for detailed analysis ⁶⁷. In addition, differential privacy (especially on a low budget) can lead to increased bias. ⁶⁸.

High Privacy Budget: Greater Utility at the Cost of Privacy

On the other hand, a high privacy budget makes it possible to generate synthetic data that bear a close resemblance to the original data. This favours more detailed analyses and more reliable results, but introduces, at the same time, a higher risk of compromising privacy.

High Fidelity: With a more generous budget, synthetic data closely reflect real data, retaining more individual detail. This increases the accuracy of analyses but raises questions about the potential re-identification of individuals ⁶⁹.

Enhanced utility: The improved accuracy of synthetic data expands their applications, allowing analysts to draw more precise conclusions and exploit the data for a wide range of research ⁷⁰.

Although the choice of a privacy budget is crucial in determining the level of protection and usefulness of synthetic data, it is important to recognise that there is no one-size-fits-all solution.

The balance between privacy and utility requires that the choice of privacy budget allocation be guided by the specific context and objectives set for the analysis.

Hence, the choice on budget allocation constitutes the inherent limitation of *differential privacy as privacy preserving guarantees* since the choice on the placement of ϵ (epsilon) directly affects the fidelity and utility properties of the generated data⁷¹.

In the generation of synthetic data, the adoption of privacy metrics is crucial to measure and ensure the security of the processed data. These metrics provide objective criteria for assessing the efficiency of strategies adopted to protect sensitive information, promoting the responsible use of synthetic data in areas such as research and development, without jeopardising the privacy of individuals in the original datasets ⁷².

Balancing the usefulness of data with its protection presents itself as a complex objective. Synthesised data must reflect the statistical properties of the original data to support

⁶⁷LI, N., QARDAJI, W., & SU, D. (2013). "On sampling, anonymization, and differential privacy or, k-anonymization meets differential privacy". In Proceedings of the 7th ACM Symposium on Information, Computer and Communications Security (pp. 32-33). ACM.

⁶⁸ GANEV, V., LI, W., SURIYAKUMAR, V., LIN, D., MIN, M. R., & YOON, J. (2022). "Revisiting pre-trained models for tabular data". In K. Chaudhuri, S. Jegelka, L. Song, C. Szepesvári, G. Niu, & S. Sabato (Eds.), Proceedings of the 39th International Conference on Machine Learning (ICML 2022), 162, 6888-6902. Retrieved from <https://proceedings.mlr.press/v162/ganev22a.html>.

⁶⁹ ABADI, M., CHU, A., GOODFELLOW, I., MCMAHAN, H. B., MIRONOV, I., TALWAR, K., & ZHANG, L. (2016). "Deep Learning with Differential Privacy". In Proceedings of the 2016 ACM SIGSAC Conference on Computer and Communications Security. ACM.

⁷⁰ MCSHERRY, F. (2009). "Privacy Integrated Queries: An Extensible Platform for Privacy-Preserving Data Analysis". In Proceedings of the 2009 ACM SIGMOD International Conference on Management of Data. ACM.

⁷¹ LEE, J., & CLIFTON, C. (2011). "How much is enough? Choosing ϵ for differential privacy". In J. Domingo-Ferrer & I. Tinnirello (Eds.), Information security (pp. 325-340). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-24861-0_22.

⁷² SOSNOVCHYK, D. (2021). "Evaluating the privacy of synthetic data using the nearest neighbor distance". (Bachelor's thesis, Freie Universität Berlin). Retrieved from <https://www.mi.fu-berlin.de/inf/groups/ag-idm/theses/2021-Sosnovchyk-BSc.pdf>.

effective predictive analysis and modelling. At the same time, however, any disclosure of personal data must be prevented.

In light of the above, the use of metrics as privacy-enhancing tools emerges as an effective strategy to address the dual challenge of protecting real data while preserving the utility and fidelity of synthetic data. This approach carefully guides the development and use of synthetic datasets in different domains, adequately satisfying both privacy requirements and analytical expectations.

The ability of synthetic data to preserve the statistical characteristics and correlations of the original dataset, while maintaining privacy, defines their usefulness.

Fidelity indicates the accuracy with which synthetic data replicate the distributions of the original data. High fidelity ensures that synthetic data can reliably replace the originals in analyses, without distorting the results due to bias. The use of specific metrics applied to different methodologies offers a way to assess the fidelity of the data.

Synthetic data should differ from the original data enough to prevent the recognisability of individuals, while maintaining a similarity that allows for valid analyses. This balancing act ensures that synthetic data remains useful and secure for the desired applications⁷³. Synthetic data, like any other type of data, can incorporate or manifest bias. This may occur during the generation phase of synthetic data, particularly if the models or algorithms used to create them learn from real data sets that already contain bias. For instance, if a real data set used to train a generative model has an unbalanced representation of certain demographic groups, it is likely that the synthetic data produced will also reflect this imbalance. In this regard, the presence of *bias* raises significant concerns, especially when such data are used to train or test artificial intelligence (AI) systems that will later be used in real-world applications. That said, *biases* may perpetuate or even amplify existing inequalities, leading to unfair or discriminatory decisions.

The techniques highlighted in this paper represent a significant commitment to the ethical and responsible generation of synthetic data, and illustrate the potential for technological advances to be governed by principles of privacy and security. Looking to the future, the necessary balance between the expansion of AI capabilities and the growing needs for personal data protection invites in-depth reflection and an ongoing commitment to research. This path, fraught with technical and ethical challenges, calls for cross-disciplinary collaboration between academics, practitioners, and legislators to ensure that the promises of the digital age are realised in a way that creates benefits for society as a whole, fostering a future where innovation and privacy go hand in hand⁷⁴.

2.8.1 Advanced synthesising methodologies

Following the analysis of different synthetic data generation methods, the focus is on the methodologies recently developed by innovative start-ups.

⁷³ EL EMAM, K., MOSQUERA, L., & HOPTRUFF, R. (n.d.). "Evaluating Synthetic Data Utility". In Practical Synthetic Data Generation. O'Reilly Media. Retrieved from <https://www.oreilly.com/library/view/practical-synthetic-data/9781492072737/cho4.html>.

⁷⁴ CASTELNOVO, A., CRUPI, R., INVERARDI, N., REGOLI, D., & COSENTINI, A. (2022). "Investigating Bias with a Synthetic Data Generator: Empirical Evidence and Philosophical Interpretation". arXiv:2209.05889v1 [stat.ML]. Recuperato il 13 settembre 2022, da <https://arxiv.org/abs/2209.05889>.

The development of a synthetic data generation methodology involves the application of generative techniques, as well as the use of appropriate tools to assess the reliability and utility of the synthetic data, while ensuring confidentiality. In the context of the evaluation of synthetic data generation methods, researchers and practitioners are exploring new methods to ensure the protection of personal data. Some techniques use learning algorithms to capture the intrinsic structures of the original data in a probabilistic way, preserving basic statistical information. A generative model, trained on the data distribution, then generates the synthetic data.

Conversely, in terms of security and privacy, distance-based metrics can be used as privacy-preserving guarantees to assess the proximity of synthetic data to real data. If the synthetic data is too similar to the real data, it is modified or removed to avoid the risk of re-identification.

Additional re-identification risk controls can be applied to the methodology to assess the possibility of re-identification attacks.

The use of such techniques and tools ensures that the synthetic data retains a high degree of fidelity to the original data, while protecting the privacy of individuals and minimising the risk of re-identification. This integrated approach makes it possible to combine the need for accurate and useful data analysis with the indispensable need to protect the rights and freedoms of individuals in accordance with current data protection legislation.

A further aspect that contributes to reducing the risks identified above is the possibility of removing specific data from the synthesising input. This is an aspect of data synthesising that does not concern the generative model itself, but rather specific early stages of the process. In particular, the synthesising of specific data may represent a point of vulnerability: the exposure of data, such as the postcodes of small towns, may facilitate the re-identification of individuals. This is of particular relevance in small communities, where the uniqueness of the postcode significantly enhances the effectiveness of re-identification algorithms. For instance, in a town with 100 residents and only one postcode, publishing synthetic data including that postcode could greatly simplify the identification of the corresponding person, as re-identification algorithms would have few candidates to consider, compromising anonymity.

Therefore, data synthesis, if properly managed through the identification and elimination of specific data categories, such as CAPs, and the adoption of appropriate evaluation metrics, offers solid protection against re-identification risks, while preserving the usefulness of the data for subsequent analysis and application.

The adoption of advanced methodologies for generating synthesised data, which include the integration of privacy-preserving safeguards, allows synthesised data to be analysed in the light of the concepts of pseudonymisation and anonymisation under the GDPR.

Therefore, where the synthetic data, while retaining the capacity to provide analytical results comparable to the original data, do not contain or reflect any specific element that could lead to the identification of the data subject, they are to be considered as anonymous data (see the EDPS guideline described in Section 2.5 above). In this scenario, as pointed out in Recital 26 of the GDPR, the processed data have undergone a process of anonymisation such that the individual is no longer identifiable, thus excluding the data from the scope of the GDPR.

Consequently, it is important to recognise that, although pseudonymisation is a remarkably effective data protection strategy, the transformation of data into a form that ensures that it is impossible to recognise the individuals involved, as illustrated above, qualifies as a form of anonymisation.

This gives synthesised data added value in terms of privacy protection, while at the same time allowing it to be used for analysis, research, and development purposes, without incurring the restrictions imposed by the GDPR. This approach aligns with the guidance provided by the EDPS, enhancing the use of synthesised data as a tool for combining innovation and privacy in the digital age.

3. Current and future regulations concerning synthetic data

3.1 Current

3.1.1 Use of health data for scientific research purposes in the GDPR (Art. 9 and 89): synthesis as an anonymisation technique?

The European Union legislation on the processing of personal data (i.e. Regulation EU 2016/679 or “GDPR”), while not expressly defining the concept of 'scientific research', draws a rather broad perimeter within which a heterogeneous range of research activities are included, such as technological development, privately financed research, and studies carried out in the public health sector (see Recital 159 of the GDPR).⁷⁵

In this regard, the European Data Protection Board also clarified that the notion of scientific research cannot be extended beyond its common meaning, to be understood primarily as a research project established in accordance with the relevant methodological and deontological sectoral standards, in line with good practice ⁷⁶.

Regardless of the exact connotation to be attributed to the field of scientific research, the European legislation, through the rules set out in the GDPR, has recognised its fundamental role within society, providing a legal system that is in some ways less strict than the general obligations established for the processing of personal data for other purposes.

Insofar as it is of interest here, the regulatory paradigm to be referred to in relation to the processing of personal data for scientific research purposes is Article 89 of the GDPR, entitled “*Safeguards and derogations relating to processing for archiving purposes in the public interest, **scientific** or historical **research purposes** or statistical purposes*”, which is both programmatic and prescriptive in nature.

Article 89(2) allows the national law of each Member State to provide for supplementary regulatory provisions, by introducing derogations and adjustments to the rights provided for in Articles 15 (“Right of access”), 16 (“Right to rectification”), 18 (“Right to restriction of processing”) and 21 (“Right to object”), provided that the exercise of those rights is likely to render impossible or seriously jeopardise the achievement of the specific purposes of the processing and that such derogations are necessary for the fulfilment of the purposes pursued by the controller.

The application of the aforementioned exceptions is, however, always subject to the implementation of specific and adequate technical and organisational measures aimed at protecting the rights and freedoms of natural persons concerned.

The system outlined by the European legislator in relation to processing operations in the field of scientific research also provides for some exceptions to the fundamental principles applicable to the processing of personal data - in particular purpose limitation and storage

⁷⁵ Recital 159 of the GDPR states that “the processing of personal data for scientific research purposes should be interpreted in a broad manner including for example technological development and demonstration, fundamental research, applied research and privately funded research. In addition, it should take into account the Union’s objective under Article 179(1) TFEU of achieving a European Research Area. Scientific research purposes should also include studies conducted in the public interest in the area of public health”.

⁷⁶ See EDPB, “Guidelines 05/2020 on consent under Regulation 2016/679” adopted on 4 May 2020.

limitation⁷⁷ - as well as some special conditions concerning the processing of personal data falling within the special categories referred to in Article 9 of the GDPR.

As known, the first point relating to purpose limitation involves the much debated issue concerning the further processing of personal data for purposes different from the initial ones (the so-called “secondary use”); moreover, such issue has already been analysed by the European Data Protection Supervisory Authorities (WP29) in their Opinion 03/2013 of 2 April 2013 (see Section 3.2.3 “Further processing for historical, statistical or scientific purposes”).

The re-use of data is explicitly allowed by Article 5(1)(b) of the GDPR, which provides for a presumption of compatibility of further processing, in the hypothesis, for instance, of processing for scientific research purposes pursuant to Article 89 of the GDPR ⁷⁸. In this respect, the European Data Protection Supervisor (“EDPS”) has provided an initial clarification⁷⁹ on the concept of presumption of compatibility enunciated in the aforementioned provision, excluding that it may constitute a general authorisation to re-use data, under any circumstances, for historical, statistical, or scientific purposes. Although the characteristics of each processing operation must be assessed on a case-by-case basis, in principle personal data collected in a given area may be further processed for scientific research purposes (by the original or a new data controller), provided that the aforementioned adequate safeguards are in place under Article 89 of the GDPR.

The second exception provided for by Article 89 of the GDPR relates to the obligation to apply a specific data retention, not exceeding the purposes specified by the data controller. This general rule is subject to a derogation that allows personal data to be stored for a longer period of time in the case of processing for scientific or historical research purposes or for archiving in the public interest or statistical purposes, provided that, in this case, appropriate technical and organisational measures are implemented to protect the rights and freedoms of the data subjects and the processing is carried out exclusively for the aforementioned purposes.

Finally, with respect to the processing of data belonging to so-called “special categories”, Article 9(2)(j) of the GDPR renders the general prohibition on processing such data non-applicable if the processing is for the purpose of scientific research and based on national or Union law, if it is proportionate to that purpose, if it respects the essence of the right to data protection, and if it provides for appropriate and specific measures to protect the fundamental rights and freedoms of the data subjects.

It should be specified, however, that with respect to the processing of genetic, biometric and health-related data, the Italian legal system, within the implementation of domestic regulatory framework in accordance with the GDPR, has exercised the power set forth in

⁷⁷ Art. 5(1)(e) GDPR: “[...] personal data may be stored for longer periods insofar as personal data will be processed solely for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes in accordance with Article 89(1) subject to implementation of the appropriate technical and organisational measures required by this Regulation in order to safeguard the rights and freedoms of the data subjects”.

⁷⁸ Art. 5(1)(b) GDPR: “...further processing for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes shall, in accordance with Article 89(1), not be considered to be incompatible with the initial purposes”.

⁷⁹ See European Data Protection Supervisor, “A Preliminary Opinion on data protection and scientific research” (6 January 2020).

Article 9(4) by inserting Article 2- *septies* into Legislative Decree 196/2003 ("Privacy Code"), through Legislative Decree n. 101/2018, which introduces additional conditions for the processing of these kind of data.

Restricting the analysis to the provisions contained in the GDPR, attention must be drawn to the guarantees required by the European legislation to protect the rights and freedoms of data subjects. The main purpose of these safeguards is to ensure the implementation of appropriate measures (technical and organisational) to protect, in particular, the principle of minimisation (see Art. 5(1)(c) GDPR).

The guarantees expressly mentioned in Article 89 of the GDPR, to be read in conjunction with Article 32 of the GDPR, include the pseudonymisation and anonymisation of personal data. In particular, from such provisions emerge a cautious approach adopted by the legislator where graduated application of these measures is established. In other words, where the purposes of scientific research can be achieved through the use of anonymous data, then use of anonymisation techniques that result in the irreversible de-identification of personal data must be favoured. Otherwise, and in a subordinate way, these safeguards could include pseudonymisation, provided that the processing allows the above-mentioned purposes to be achieved, always in compliance with the principle of minimisation.

In order for personal data to be considered anonymous, it must in fact undergo a process of anonymisation according to the techniques provided for by the European Supervisory Authorities - e.g. masking, randomisation, generalisation, etc. - as well as according to the new ISO/IEC 27559:2022 standard "Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection - Privacy enhancing data de-identification framework". - as well as according to the new standard ISO/IEC 27559:2022 "Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection - Privacy enhancing data de-identification framework".

The assessment of the effectiveness of the anonymisation process adopted from time to time shall ultimately also have to consider the specific indications provided in the measures of the national Supervisory Authorities ⁸⁰, as well as (national and European) case law ⁸¹.

In the field of scientific research - in particular health research - the importance of having a data set with quality and completeness characteristics is well known, as these elements are fundamental prerequisites for accurate and effective studies and research. However, these requirements must necessarily be reconciled with the need to protect the confidentiality of the data subjects and the information concerning them.

With this regard, it is well known that a completely anonymous dataset may have certain limitations that stem, above all, from the reduced accuracy of the analyses carried out on such data and the loss of relationships between them.

For these reasons, in support of scientific research (in particular health research), innovative methods are spreading that involve the use of so-called synthetic data created on the basis of statistical models processed by an artificial intelligence algorithm, which can provide an alternative solution to 'traditional' anonymisation.

The use of synthetic data therefore seems to be an extremely interesting solution for companies in the technology sector (healthcare but not only) that need to process and

⁸⁰ See *ex multis* Prov. GPDP No. 226 of 1 June 2023 ("ThinS.r.l." case).

⁸¹ Cf. EU General Court - Case T-557-20, which partially overrode the principles expressed by WP29 in Opinion 05/2014.

analyse large amounts of data, and in particular for companies developing artificial intelligence systems that require a large volume of data for algorithm training.

A further critical element, from a legal point of view, concerns the initial phase of processing “real” personal data used to build the model that will enable the AI system to generate non-personal synthetic data and train it.

The use of personal data for the development of learning models or for the training of generative AI systems represents, in fact, a typical case of data processing for secondary purposes that are further and different from the original ones; in such case, limiting the analysis to the health and scientific research in the health field, the requirements of Article 89 of the GDPR and of the relevant national legislation should apply.

An additional important aspect to be considered is the correct identification of the legal basis of the processing, given that, as already pointed out, the transformation of real data into synthetic data constitutes a further processing that requires a valid legal basis in order to render the processing itself lawful. The Spanish Supervisory Authority (*Agencia Española de Protección de Datos - AEPD*) has also clearly expressed itself on this point, emphasising that the creation of synthetic data from real data constitutes a processing regulated by the GDPR. Therefore, it is necessary to take into account European data protection law - and, in particular, the principle of accountability - and to assess the risk of possible re-identification of data subjects from the synthetic data set that has been created ⁸².

Lastly, it should be noted that, as regards the issue of the use of synthetic data, to date there is no organic set of rules or guidelines drawn up by the European Data Protection Board or the European Supervisory Authorities. In this sense, limiting the analysis to the Italian panorama, it is desirable that the Italian Supervisory Authority - “*Garante per la protezione dei dati personali*” - provide some clarifications and interpretative guidelines and indicate clear rules for the operations involving synthesis of personal data that are not limited to IT technicalities, but also cover the legal aspects of processing - for example identifying the legal bases legitimising the transformation of real data into synthetic data - especially with reference to those areas in which the use of synthetic data is to be regarded as crucial (e.g. synthetic data obtained from health-related data and used in the field of scientific research)⁸³.

3.1.2 Data Governance Act and synthetic data: right to re-use (recital 15 and Art. 5 of the DGA)

Regulation (EU) 2022/868 on European data governance (hereafter, “**Data Governance Act**” or “**DGA**”) of 30 May 2022 represents an essential component of the “*regulatory framework*” of the “European Data Strategy”, which aims to create a European digital space where data (also of a non-personal nature) can be used independently of their physical location in the Union so as to allow them to be shared between different parties (public and private) and increase the availability of information, especially within strategic sectors (e.g. health, environment, energy, agriculture, financial services, etc.).

⁸² See AEPD Communiqué of 11.02.2023.

⁸³ LUCA BOLOGNINI, “*Un focus su dati sintetici e privacy, con proposte evolutive di soft regulation*”, Giuffrè Francis Lefebvre.

It is important to point out that the new European regulation does not apply only to personal data (according to the meaning provided for in the GDPR), but extends to additional information that includes "*...any digital representation of acts, facts or information and any compilation of such acts, facts or information, including in the form of sound, visual and audiovisual recording*" (see definition of "data" under Article 2(1) of the DGA).

The DGA is based on three essential pillars: i. the re-use⁸⁴ of data held by public bodies⁸⁵; ii. the voluntary sharing of data on the basis of so-called "data altruism"⁸⁶ with the aim of creating a single market for data and enhancing the value of data; and iii. the regulation of data intermediation services.

The core principles concerning the re-use of data are contained in recital 15 and Article 5 of the DGA, while the categories of data covered by the right of re-use are defined in detail in Article 3.

More specifically, the DGA applies to data held by public sector bodies - identified in the Regulations as "data holders" - that are protected for reasons of: i. commercial confidentiality (including trade, professional or business secrets); ii. statistical confidentiality; iii. protection of third parties' intellectual property; and iv. protection of personal data (unless covered by Directive (EU) 2019/1024 on the re-use of public sector information).

The DGA provides, however, for certain categories of data that are instead excluded from the possibility of re-use. This refers in particular to the following types of data: i. data held by public undertakings⁸⁷; ii. data held by public service broadcasters or other bodies and their subsidiaries for the fulfilment of a public service broadcasting task; iii. data held by cultural and educational bodies; iv. data held by public bodies and protected for reasons of public security, defence or national security, and v. data whose provision is not part of the public service tasks of the public bodies concerned.

Turning to the focus of this contribution, i.e. the re-use of data (in particular synthetic data), it is noted that the DGA has established rules and safeguards to facilitate such re-use, allowing the extraction of information from such data, without compromising its protected nature.

The legal examination of the re-use of data should start from Article 5 of the DGA - to be read in conjunction with recital 15 - in order to outline the rules that must be complied with.

⁸⁴ According to Article 2(2) of the DGA, "re-use" means: "*the use by natural or legal persons of data held by public sector bodies, for commercial or non-commercial purposes other than the initial purpose within the public task for which the data were produced, except for the exchange of data between public sector bodies purely in pursuit of their public tasks*".

⁸⁵ According to Article 2(17) of the DGA are regarded as public bodies "*the State, regional or local authorities, bodies governed by public law or associations formed by one or more of such authorities, or one or more such bodies governed by public law*".

⁸⁶ Article 2(16) of the DGA provides the following definition of "altruism of data": "*the voluntary sharing of data on the basis of the consent of data subjects to process personal data pertaining to them, or permissions of data holders to allow the use of their non-personal data without seeking or receiving a reward that goes beyond compensation related to the costs that they incur when they make their data available for objectives of general interest as provided for in national law, where applicable, such as healthcare, combating climate change, improving mobility, facilitating the development, production and dissemination of official statistics, improving the provision of public services, public policy making or scientific research purposes in the general interest*".

⁸⁷ Article 2(19) of the DGA defines public undertakings as: "*any undertaking over which the public sector bodies may exercise directly or indirectly a dominant influence by virtue of their ownership of it, their financial participation therein, or the rules which govern it [...]*".

In particular, the aforementioned provisions require that the conditions for the re-use of data meet certain criteria - in short, they must be non-discriminatory, transparent and proportionate - and, moreover, be supported by a substantiated motivation with regard to the nature and categories of data as well as the purposes of their re-use.

It should be noted how the DGA, while focusing on data protection aspects and on the measures and safeguards to be applied to data re-use, pays at the same time the utmost attention to competition between undertakings, which may in no way be restricted by the conditions laid down for the right to re-use data. Likewise, the same rules to be applied to the re-use of data must not restrict, but facilitate, the promotion and development of scientific research.

As to the measures to be applied to ensure adequate protection to data, an obligation is placed on public sector bodies to ensure that the data requested for re-use are anonymised (only in the case of personal data) and that, in the case of confidential business information (including trade secrets and content protected by intellectual property rights), they are appropriately edited, aggregated or otherwise handled with appropriate disclosure controls.

From a literal interpretation of the provisions of Article 5, it seems that, as far as personal data are concerned, the pseudonymisation envisaged by the GDPR as a technical security measure is not sufficient to obtain access to the data for their re-use, since compliance with the conditions set out in the GDPR is linked to the implementation of "appropriate anonymisation". It should be noted, however, that recital 15 provides instead that the transmission of pseudonymised data (including personal data) to third parties for re-use may be allowed, provided that it is impossible to re-identify the data subjects.

That said, with a view to facilitating the exchange of data and their re-use, the DGA also contemplates two alternative options for legitimate access to information held by a public sector body: i. remote access to a secure processing environment provided or controlled by a public sector body; or ii. re-use of data in a secure processing environment located at the physical premises of a public sector body. In all cases, stringent security measures must be implemented.

Among the techniques that the DGA considers suitable for ensuring the protection of personal data and reducing the risk of identification of data subjects, the use of synthetic data is expressly mentioned (see recital 7). In this respect, the openness of the European legislation to the use of data obtained through synthesis, the application of which is put on an equal footing with other techniques such as anonymisation or differential privacy, in terms of protecting the privacy of individuals, is certainly significant.

In other words, data synthesis could be used, in the areas identified by the DGA, as an effective anonymisation technique to access, analyse, share, re-use and publish data without revealing personal information. Data synthesis is seen, in this sense, as a tool that respects data protection requirements and at the same time stimulates technological innovation.

If, on the one hand, the application of such techniques is already able to ensure greater security in the use and re-use of personal data as well as confidential business information for statistical, research and innovation purposes, it should also be noted that the DGA, in

order to further protect the data subjects and their data, requires in certain cases the performance of further obligations by the public data holders, with the possible involvement of the national Supervisory Authorities. This is the case, for instance, provided for in recital 15, where it is stated that, if the provision of anonymised data does not meet the needs of the re-user, before granting re-use of the data on-site or remotely in a secure processing environment, public sector bodies are obliged to carry out a data protection impact assessment and, if necessary, to consult the competent Supervisory Authority in accordance with Articles 35 and 36 of the GDPR.

Proceeding further in the analysis of the cornerstones of the DGA, the tasks attributed to specific figures in the new legislation, such as 'data intermediation service providers', come to the fore.

Data intermediation services, defined in Article 2(11) of the DGA, have the main purpose of establishing business relationships to share data between data holders and data subjects on the one hand and data users on the other.

More in detail, the types of data intermediation services identified by the DGA are the following: i. intermediation services between data holders and potential data users: such services may include bilateral or multilateral exchanges of data or the creation of platforms or databases allowing for the exchange or joint use of data, as well as specific infrastructures for the interconnection of data holders with data users; ii. intermediary services between data subjects/natural persons and potential data users: such services, in addition to assistance activities, may include the provision of technical means to enable, in particular, the exercise of data subjects' rights under the GDPR; and iii. data cooperative services: such services are offered by an organisational structure made up of data subjects, sole proprietorships, or SMEs, in order to assist its members in exercising their rights in relation to certain data and in negotiating terms and conditions for the processing of the same data⁸⁸.

It is worth noting that the DGA requires that intermediation services be provided through a separate legal entity, thereby effectively imposing a structural separation of such services. The rationale of this provision clearly lies in the European legislator's desire to prevent companies providing information society services from taking advantage of the information and data collected through the intermediation activity.

The regulatory framework devised in the DGA also requires that data intermediation services providers follow a specific notification procedure to the competent authority for intermediation services identified by each EU Member State. The notification must contain the information exhaustively listed in Article 11(6) of the DGA, including, by way of example, the name of the provider of intermediation services, its legal form, ownership structure, registered office, description of the data intermediation service, etc.

The competent Authority for data intermediation services is then obliged to inform the European Commission without delay of any new notification received.

⁸⁸ ELISABETTA NUNZIANTE, "Data Governance Act, from September the new rules start", Risk Management 360, 05.07.2023.

The competent Authorities, in addition to being responsible for the notification process, must also be in charge of monitoring the compliance of data intermediation services with the requirements of the DGA, including taking penalty measures and ordering the suspension or cessation of the activity in case of violations.

As can easily be guessed, the above-mentioned obligations are of crucial importance for providers of data intermediation services, since on the successful outcome of the notification procedure depends on the actual possibility for them to conduct their business and provide such services in accordance with the DGA.

In this regard, recently Law No. 15 of 21 February 2024 on “*Delegation to the Government for the transposition of European directives and the implementation of other acts of the European Union - European Delegation Law 2022 – 202*”, at Article 17 has delegated the Italian Government to adopt, within four months from the entry into force of the aforementioned law (i.e., by July 2024), the regulatory acts - i.e., legislative decrees - for the adaptation of the national legislation to the DGA. In compliance with the aforementioned regulatory provisions, on 3 July 2024 the Italian Government approved the draft legislative decree introducing rules for the compliance of national legislation to the provisions of the DGA. In particular, as far as it is of interest here, the decree designates the Agency for Digital Italy (AgID) as the competent authority responsible to carry out the tasks related to the notification procedure for data intermediation services as well as the competent authority for the registration of data altruism organisations. AgID is also designated as the competent authority to assist public bodies granting or refusing access to the re-use of specific categories of data.

3.1.3 Data Act: access to data

The Regulation (EU) 2023/2854 on harmonised rules on fair access to and use of data and amending Regulation (EU) 2017/2394 and Directive (EU) 2020/1828 (so-called “**Data Act**”), which entered into force on 11 January 2024 and is going to be applicable from 12 September 2025, like the DGA (previously reviewed), is a key pillar of the 'European Data Strategy', introducing new, harmonised rules on access to and use of data from connected products. The aim of the Data Act - and of the broader EU Data Strategy - is to facilitate reliable and secure access to data (of a personal and non-personal nature), promoting their use in key economic sectors and areas of public interest.

The subjective scope of the Data Act is very broad and concerns, first of all, manufacturers of connected products placed on the European market, providers of related services, providers of Data Processing Services (DPS) - irrespective of their place of establishment - data holders, public bodies and, of course, users in the European Union of such products or services.

Excluded from the scope of the Data Act are micro and small enterprises, unless they are part of a business group such as affiliated or subsidiary enterprises.

As mentioned, the broad concept of 'data' - borrowed from the Data Governance Act - also includes personal data as defined in Article 4(11) of the GDPR. Consequently, if the user's data are of a personal nature, EU data protection law must be applied, together with the

provisions of the Data Act, insofar as they are compatible (the provisions of the GDPR, in fact, must be deemed to prevail in the event of a conflict).

With regard to the subject of the accessibility of the data regulated by the Data Act, it is interesting to note how Article 3 introduces, for the first time, the concept of accessibility of the data "by design and by default", meaning that the connected products and the related services must be designed and developed, if technically possible, in such a way as to allow the users to easily and directly access the information generated by such product (e.g. a device) or service. In this respect, one of the main innovations introduced by the Data Act concerning the right of access by users to their own data must be found in Article 4⁸⁹, which provides that, if the data of the connected product or of the related service are not directly accessible by a user, the data holder is obliged, without delay, to make such data and related metadata available in compliance with the conditions laid down by the aforementioned provision (i.e. easily, securely, free of charge, etc.).

Among the relevant aspects that emerge from the aforementioned provision is the fact that all data generated, for example, by an IoT system, which are not yet in the user's control, must now be made accessible by the data holder at the times and in the ways defined by the Regulation. This means that, in the event that the data generated by the system are not in the user's control, the user will have the right to receive a copy of the data in a structured format and under the conditions laid down in the Regulation.

The new European legislation provides, by way of derogation from the broad right of access already mentioned, that access to data, as well as their use and further sharing, may be subject to a limitation or even to an explicit prohibition laid down by the user or data holder within a contract, provided that the processing may compromise the security requirements of the related product and entail serious harm to the health, safety or protection of natural persons. In this context, it cannot be ruled out that the use of synthetic data could be a valid solution to overcome such limitations or prohibitions on the processing of data in the terms outlined above; on the other hand, from a contractual point of view, it could be provided in a contract that the limitation or prohibition on processing in the terms set out above, does not apply if the data in question undergo a process of synthesis so as to prevent their use from undermining the safety requirements of the product or the health and safety of natural persons.

Regardless of the exceptions discussed above, the regulatory provisions of the Data Act governing the right of access can be seen to have certain advantages that could solve a problem common to many technological products: one refers, in particular, to the need to carry out repairs, maintenance and updates only with the manufacturers themselves or authorised resellers of such products, since the relevant data, which would allow to

⁸⁹ Article 4(1) of the Data Act provides that: "Where data cannot be directly accessed by the user from the connected product or related service, data holders shall make readily available data, as well as the relevant metadata necessary to interpret and use those data, accessible to the user without undue delay, of the same quality as is available to the data holder, easily, securely, free of charge, in a comprehensive, structured, commonly used and machine-readable format and, where relevant and technically feasible, continuously and in real time. This shall be done on the basis of a simple request through electronic means where technically feasible".

understand the functioning of the system, are not disclosed by the manufacturer because it considers them to be information covered by “trade secrets”.

On this point, the rules of the Data Act stipulate that trade secrets may be disclosed provided that all specific measures are taken to preserve the confidentiality of the data shared, in particular towards third parties. These measures, to be agreed upon between data holder and user, may consist of specific contractual clauses, confidentiality agreements, codes of conduct, etc.

Access to data that constitute “trade secrets” does, however, provide for certain exceptions, for example where the data holder, who has specific rights on a trade secret, is able to demonstrate a high probability of suffering patrimonial damages as a result of disclosure, despite the fact that technical and organisational measures are taken by the user. In such cases, the data holder may refuse to comply with a request for access to such data pursuant to Article 4(7) of the Data Act.

To further protect the data holder, there is also a non-compete provision to prevent misuse by the user of the data obtained under the Data Act: according to this provision, the user is prohibited from using the data to which he has had access following a specific request under Article 4(1) to develop a related product in competition with the product from which the data originate; nor may the user share the data with a third party or use them to obtain information on the economic situation, resources and production methods of the manufacturer or data holder. The latter provision is counterbalanced, in a symmetrical manner, by Article 4(13), which places a limit on the use of user-generated data, providing that the data holder may only have access to and use any non-personal data generated by the use of a product or a related service on the basis of a contractual agreement with the user and, at the same time, may not use such data to obtain information on the user's economic situation, assets and production methods or on the user's use of them that could jeopardise the user's commercial position in the markets in which it operates.

On the one hand, therefore, the user cannot exploit the data in order to become a competitor of the data holder, as this would be an unfair practice and, in this respect, the Data Act is intended to prevent the right of access from being used as a pretext to unlawfully obtain trade secrets and company information in order to gain a commercial advantage. On the other hand, at the same time, it is ensured that user-generated data are governed by a contract with the data holder, prohibiting the latter from unfairly exploiting the user's data and thus undermining the position in the market.

It is easy to see how the introduction of the right of access to data will have a significant impact on both large companies and SMEs, but also on individuals.

One area of application of the Data Act of undoubted relevance is digital health. In this regard, in fact, any medical or wearable device connected to the Internet of Things (IoT) that collects, generates, and processes data of the person using it, or relating to his or her environment, falls within the scope of the Data Act. Medical and health devices are also expressly mentioned in the legislation, and most digital health stakeholders, such as manufacturers of medical devices (including wearables), as well as providers of related

services, will be subject to the Data Act when the product or service is placed on the EU market.

3.2 Future

3.2.1 Synthetic data in the AI Act (Articles 10 and 59)

Following the provisional agreement on the proposal for a European Regulation containing harmonised rules on Artificial Intelligence (so-called. "**Artificial Intelligence Act**" or "**AI Act**") reached on 9 December 2023 between the Presidency of the Council of the European Union and the negotiators of the European Parliament, and the subsequent agreement on the final text reached on 2 February 2024 by Coreper (Committee of Permanent Representatives of the Governments of the Member States of the European Union), the legislative process on the AI Act was concluded with the approval of the consolidated act by the European Parliament and the final approval by the EU Council on 21 May 2024. The regulation was published in the Official Journal of the European Union on 12 July 2024 and will enter into force in the next 20 days. The new regulation will apply two years after its entry into force, from 2 August 2026, with some exceptions relating to specific cases.

The AI Act, which is rightly intended to represent a milestone in EU legislation, has the primary objective of promoting the development and adoption throughout the EU single market, by both public and private parties, of safe and reliable Artificial Intelligence, which will have to be subject to strict rules according to a risk-based approach.

The topic we intend to explore relates to the use of synthetic data and their regulation in the AI Act, in particular in Articles 10 – "*Data and data governance*" - and 59 – "*Further processing of personal data for developing certain AI systems in the public interest in the AI regulatory sandbox*".

As a preliminary remark, it must be pointed out that the spread of Artificial Intelligence systems has given rise to the need for the European legislator to regulate the use of such tools, and in particular to provide specific rules aimed at punctually regulating the aspects related to the protection of personal data, placing the protection of individuals' fundamental rights and freedoms at the centre.

As also noted by the Advisory Committee of the Convention for the Protection of Individuals with regard to the Processing of Personal Data (Convention 108), responsible innovation in the field of Artificial Intelligence requires an approach that focuses on mitigating and eliminating the potential risks of processing personal data ⁹⁰.

In its Guidelines, the Advisory Committee already emphasised the importance for developers, producers, and providers of AI services to adopt an approach aimed at protecting human rights from the design of such services (so-called "*human rights design*"), avoiding any potential *bias*, even unintentional or hidden, as well as risks of discrimination or other negative effects on the fundamental rights and freedoms of natural persons. Hence

⁹⁰ See also "*Guidelines on Artificial Intelligence and data protection*" of 25 January 2019.

the need for developers to use only accurate and quality datasets, reducing excess, unnecessary or marginal data during the development and training phases of the system.

In its policy paper, the Committee mentions synthetic data, indicating their use as an appropriate solution to “minimise” the amount of real personal data processed by “intelligent” applications.

On this point, it should be added that through synthesised data - depending on the methodology used in the synthesisation process - it is also possible to prevent the retrieval of information that would make it possible to trace back the data subjects (thus ensuring the non-reversibility of de-identification) and to overcome certain restrictive requirements laid down by data protection legislation.

It should be noted how the AI Act refers to synthetic and anonymous data in terms of equivalence. This can be seen from Article 59, which regulates the conditions that, in the so-called “AI regulatory sandbox” ⁹¹, must be met in order to be able to re-use for the sole purpose of developing, training, and testing AI systems personal data previously collected for other purposes. Basically, from a literal interpretation of paragraph 1(b) of the above-mentioned provision, the use of synthetic data (in the same way as anonymous and non-personal data) should be considered prevalent - and preferable, subject to exceptions - in meeting the requirements of the AI Act for AI systems classified as “high risk” ⁹². Indeed, the AI Act seems to equate synthetic data with data of a non-personal nature: in this regard, should be noted the use in Article 59(1)(b) itself of the term “other non-personal data”, preceded by the reference to synthetic data (as well as anonymous data), from which it is possible to infer the assimilation of the latter types of data to the category of non-personal data.

In order to put these intelligent systems on the market, the AI Act lays down a number of stringent obligations for developers and manufacturers due to their particular characteristics. These obligations include, first and foremost, the establishment and maintenance of an adequate risk management and data governance system to ensure the robustness, security, and accuracy of AI systems. The possibility of correcting or deactivating the system in the event of errors or risks must also be guaranteed, and supervisory mechanisms must be in place as well as the possibility of ensuring human intervention to prevent or mitigate damage or negative impacts on the rights and freedoms of individuals.

Before the system is placed on the market, it is also necessary to prepare complete technical documentation to demonstrate the conformity of the Artificial Intelligence system with the requirements of the European legislation and, at the same time, a register must be set up to ensure the traceability of the system's operation throughout its market period.

⁹¹ The term “*AI Regulatory sandbox*” refers to “controlled” environments, established by a relevant authority, in which AI systems are developed, trained and tested according to a plan agreed between the AI system developer and the authority itself.

⁹² The term “*high-risk*” artificial intelligence systems refers to AI systems used as safety components of a product, those that are themselves a product, covered by EU health and safety legislation and, finally, those that fall under the areas listed in Annex III of the AI Act (e.g. biometric remote identification systems).

Article 10 of the AI Act lays down strict quality criteria that data used as a basis for the development of high-risk AI systems in the training, validation and testing phases must possess.

Obligations pertaining to the management and verification of data used for the development of AI systems include the analysis of possible biases that could affect the health and safety of individuals, or have a negative impact on fundamental rights, or even lead to discrimination. To reduce these risks, the application of appropriate measures to identify, prevent and mitigate possible biases is required. The data sets used must also be relevant, sufficiently representative, and, as far as possible, error-free, and as complete as possible in view of the purposes pursued and must possess appropriate statistical properties.

Article 10(5) authorises providers of high-risk artificial intelligence systems, to the extent strictly necessary to ensure the detection and correction of *bias*, to exceptionally process personal data belonging to the special categories referred to in Articles 9(1) of Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR), 10 of Directive (EU) 2016/680 and 10(1) of Regulation (EU) 2018/1725. However, such processing must be subject to appropriate safeguards for the fundamental rights and freedoms of natural persons, including technical limitations on re-use and the use of state-of-the-art security and privacy measures.

The provision in question identifies the mandatory conditions that constitute a prerequisite for the processing of special data for the above-mentioned purposes. The first of these conditions - which must be met cumulatively - states that the processing of particular data under Article 10 is permitted only if its purpose, i.e. the detection and correction of harm, cannot be effectively achieved by the processing of synthetic or anonymised data. Conversely, if an Artificial Intelligence system provider is able to detect and correct bias using synthetic or anonymised data, it is obliged to do so and cannot rely on other “appropriate safeguards”.

The second necessary condition relates to the application of technical limitations on the re-use of special categories of personal data, as well as more advanced security and privacy-preserving measures, including pseudonymisation.

It is also necessary for special data to be subject to measures to ensure adequate security of processing as well as appropriate safeguards - including traceable data access controls - in order to prevent misuse and ensure that only authorised persons, with specific confidentiality obligations, have access to such personal data (the reference is, of course, to the persons authorised to process the data as referred to in Articles 29, 32(4) of the GDPR and 2-*quaterdecies* of the Privacy Code).

As further conditions to be fulfilled in order to fall within the exemption to the prohibition of the processing of special categories of personal data, the provision in question provides for an explicit prohibition of transmission, transfer or consultation by third parties of this category of personal data, as well as the obligation to delete personal data after the *bias* has been corrected or once the established retention period has expired (whichever comes first).

Finally, there is a further obligation to record in the register of processing operations the reasons why the processing of special categories of personal data was necessary, specifying the reasons why the same result could not be achieved by processing other types of data.

In this context, it seems that the European legislator identifies the use of synthetic data - together with anonymised data - as the preferred method for detecting and resolving data *biases* in the development of high-risk AI systems. It should also be added that synthetic data, if used to replace personal data, can provide an important aid to the development of *data governance* and cybersecurity processes with a view to mitigating risks arising from the use of artificial intelligence systems, including high-risk ones. It is also worth noting how the recognition of synthetic data as non-personal data encourages the use of this generative technology in a wide range of applications, to the benefit of scientific research and public policy planning - particularly in the field of health -, given that synthesis makes it possible to share, store and re-use data for purposes of public interest other than those initially pursued - i.e. at the time of data acquisition -, while at the same time guaranteeing the protection of the right to personal data protection.

Providers and users of AI systems should implement state-of-the-art technical and organisational measures to protect these rights. These measures should include not only anonymisation and encryption, but also the use of increasingly available technologies that allow algorithms to be applied to data and valuable information to be extracted from it without the unnecessary transmission between parties or copying of the raw or structured data themselves.

Finally, it should be noted that the legal value attributed to synthetic data through the inclusion in the IA Act of regulatory provisions explicitly concerning them is to be seen as a confirmation of the growing political awareness of the potential of this technology. This is underlined by a recent report by the European Commission's Joint Research Centre (JRC), which states that synthetic data can not only be shared freely but can also help rebalance underrepresented classes in research studies through oversampling, making them a perfect input for machine learning and AI models⁹³.

3.2.2 European Health Data Space: Proposal for a Regulation

On 24 April 2024, following the agreement reached with the Council of the European Union, the European Parliament approved the text of the Regulation establishing the European Health Data Space (hereafter, only “EHDS”), which is intended to bring about radical changes in the management of health data within the EU Member States.

The EHDS represents a significant opportunity to make better use of large quantities of health data that are currently difficult to access, with the priority aim of creating a common European space, with interoperable standards and facilitated access to health data for both primary use (provision of health services) and secondary uses.

The Explanatory Memorandum to the Regulation highlighted how, at present, individuals encounter difficulties in exercising their rights over their electronic health data (e.g. in exercising their right of access and in their national and cross-border transmission), mainly due to the uneven implementation and interpretation by the Member States of the GDPR's rules on the processing of health data, with the consequent determination of legal uncertainties that can create obstacles to the secondary use of health data. Moreover, also

⁹³ See JRC Technical Report, “*Multipurpose synthetic population for policy applications*”, 13.06.2022.

due to the heterogeneity of national laws and limited interoperability, manufacturers of eHealth products and eHealth service providers operating in one Member State encounter difficulties and additional costs when accessing data stored in another Member State.

Allowing wider re-use of health data would therefore bring benefits and improvements in the areas of scientific research, innovation, and patient safety, among others.

Having said that, it should be noted that the Regulation lays down rather stringent requirements for access to and secondary use of electronic health data held by a “data holder”⁹⁴.

Among the various secondary purposes that can be pursued by the applicant through the processing of health data - in particular, those contained in electronic health records - the EHDS also expressly includes training, testing and evaluation activities of algorithms, including those relating to medical devices, AI systems and digital health applications, that contribute to public health or social security, or that ensure high levels of quality and safety of healthcare, medicines or medical devices.

According to the above-mentioned legal provisions, the applicant (data user) who wishes to access electronic health data (of a personal and non-personal nature) held by a data holder for secondary use must be able to prove that access is necessary for one of the purposes explicitly referred to in the EHDS (see Art. 34).

The EHDS also prohibits the processing of electronic health data for secondary uses for a number of purposes, such as: i. making decisions prejudicial to an individual on the basis of his or her electronic health data; ii. excluding an individual or group of individuals from benefits arising from an insurance contract or changing their insurance contributions and premiums; iii. develop products or services that may harm individuals and society at large, including, but not limited to illicit drugs, tobacco, alcoholic beverages; iv. carry out advertising or marketing activities directed at health care professionals, health care organisations or individuals; v. provide access to, or otherwise make available, electronic health data to third parties not mentioned in the data use authorisation.

The EHDS provides for a rather extensive list of minimum categories of electronic health data that data holders must make available for re-use, including electronic health records, human genetic, genomic, and proteomic data, identification data relating to health professionals involved in patient care, electronic health data from clinical trials, electronic health data from biobanks, etc.

In the request for access to electronic health data for secondary use, which is to be submitted to one or more health data access body responsible for granting access to health data designated by each Member State, the user is obliged to provide a number of elements, including a detailed explanation of the intended use of such data and an indication of the

⁹⁴ Art. 2(y) of the proposed EHDS defines “data holder” as “any natural or legal person which is an entity or a body in the health or care sector, or performing research in relation to these sectors, as well as Union institutions, bodies, offices and agencies who has the right or obligation, in accordance with this Regulation, applicable Union law or national legislation implementing Union law, or in the case of non-personal data, through control of the technical design of a product and related services, the ability to make available, including to register, provide, restrict access or exchange certain data”.

purposes pursued, among those provided for by the Regulation; moreover, among the information that must be contained in the request for access, it is necessary to indicate whether the request relates to anonymised or pseudonymised data. The distinction is not insignificant, since if the data to which the user wishes to have access are anonymised, the EHDS provides for a “simplified” procedure for obtaining authorisation from the health data access body. Conversely, if the user needs access to pseudonymised health data only - i.e. data of a personal nature to which personal data protection legislation is applicable - the applicant is required to provide some additional information, including the justification on which the request for access is based, explaining why anonymised data are not sufficient to pursue the stated purpose. Where electronic personal health data are made available in pseudonymised form, the encryption key may only be held by the body responsible for accessing the health data.

Furthermore, in the request for access to health data, applicant is obliged to identify the legal basis of the processing under Article 6 of the GDPR (namely, the exercise of a public interest task or legitimate interest), as well as, possibly, an ethical assessment based on national law.

In addition, the EHDS assigns public interest tasks to the bodies responsible for access to health data under Article 6(1)(e) of the GDPR and, at the same time, provides the legal basis and fulfils the conditions for processing under Article 9(2)(g), (h), (i) and (j) of the GDPR. Therefore, if the request submitted by the user for access to electronic health data is based on Article 6(1)(e) of the GDPR, he/she will have to indicate the national or European Union law that makes the processing of electronic health data legitimate, whereas, if the request is based on Article 6(1)(f) of the GDPR, it is the EHDS itself that provide the necessary guarantees, since the authorisations for secondary use of the data issued by the health data access bodies have the legal nature of an administrative decision that precisely defines the conditions for accessing the data (see Cons. 37).

As mentioned above, access requests are handled by a single health data access body. Data users wishing to access electronic health data from more than one Member State have to submit a single application to one of the health data access bodies of their choice. However, if an applicant wishes to access electronic health data held by a single data holder, he may submit a data access application or request directly to that data holder.

Health data access bodies must allow or refuse authorisation within two months of receipt of the application for access to the data (extendable by a further two months). If the body does not take a decision within the deadline, the authorisation is granted, thus applying a form of silence - assent. The data authorisation sets out the general conditions applicable to the user of the data, including the types and format of electronic health data accessed, the purpose of the making available, the duration of the authorisation, etc. Once the request has been granted, the health data access body will request the data from the holder, who must provide it to the user within two months.

Finally, users have to make public the results or outputs related to the secondary use of electronic health data, including information relevant to the provision of health care, within eighteen months of the completion of the processing.

3.2.3 Synthetic data and digital health: prospects for use in the Italian regulatory landscape

In the Italian digital health landscape, the health sector is plagued by structural inefficiencies, mainly due to regional disparities and suboptimal data management. These shortcomings hinder the effective evolution of the system, despite the urgent need for digital progress. In this scenario, the use of synthetic data is emerging as a potentially revolutionary solution that could align healthcare planning with operational realities while, in principle, protecting the privacy of individuals.

Synthetic data, processed using sophisticated artificial intelligence techniques, retains the statistical properties of the original data while excluding potentially identifying elements. This process, which ensures the protection of personal data, has several advantages: on the one hand, it allows in-depth analysis and health policy formulation based on a realistic and up-to-date database; on the other hand, it reduces the risks associated with the direct handling of sensitive patient data. However, the use of synthetic data requires careful ethical and regulatory considerations to ensure that the use of such technologies is consistent with the principles of justice and equity.⁹⁵

The regulatory landscape for the use of synthetic data in the Italian healthcare sector is part of a broader context of European and national regulation aimed at balancing technological innovation with privacy and data security.

The generation and use of synthetic data poses new regulatory challenges, particularly in terms of data protection. This technology, while promising significant benefits in healthcare, requires a careful assessment of the associated risks and benefits, as well as the adoption of an appropriate legal framework to regulate their use in an effective and secure manner. Professor Pasquale Stanzione, President of the Data Protection Authority, highlighted the tension between the need for confidentiality and the need for research and innovation in the health sector, emphasising the need to find a balance in the current digital context. The reflection on the use of health data seems to be a two-sided coin: on the one hand, the use of these data is fundamental for progress and innovation in the field of health; on the other hand, there is an urgent need to protect health data, which are considered "hypersensitive"⁹⁶.

Indeed, Professor Stanzione's reflection underline the importance of a strong synergy between technological advancement, data protection rules and healthcare management policies. Balancing those needs is therefore a *conditio sine qua non* for ensuring that the development of the healthcare sector respect the rights and dignity of patients.

In the Italian healthcare context, the use of synthesised data represents valuable tool for increasing the quality and efficiency of healthcare provision, ensuring equitable access to innovations. Synthesising techniques help to overcome several scenarios that have a significant impact on machine learning models, such as the shortage of information,

⁹⁵ SCORZA, G. (2024, 5 February). The right not to have to choose between more privacy and more health. *Il Sole 24 Ore*.

⁹⁶ Chamber of Deputies - Commission XII Social Affairs. (2024, February 13). Informal hearing of the President of the Italian Data Protection Authority, Prof. Pasquale Stanzione - Consideration of Resolutions Loizzo No. 7-00183 and Girelli No. 7-00183 on the collection and use of health data. Chamber of Deputies.

especially for rare or poorly studied diseases. At the same time, the use of synthetic data makes it possible to design and develop broader and more inclusive research. To this aim, the generation of large datasets facilitates the development of accurate predictive and diagnostic models, shortening the time it takes to transfer scientific discoveries to the clinical field and promoting a more personalised and preventive approach in medicine⁹⁷. With regard to the value of using synthetic data in the health sector a study was carried out in 2020 to develop a methodology capable of generating CT (Computed Tomography) images related to COVID-19 through the use of conditional generative adversarial networks (cGANs) ⁹⁸. Jiang's research aimed to produce high-quality, realistic CT images, which are essential for training deep learning techniques in medical imaging. The primary reason for the researchers to use synthetic data in addition to real data was the high prevalence and contagiousness of the virus, which made it difficult to collect a sufficient amount of real data for training purposes. Therefore, the use of synthetic data was therefore essential to compensate for the lack of information. In addition, the synthetic data helped to mitigate the dangers to healthcare workers of contracting the virus. This research demonstrated the effectiveness of the cGAN-based strategy over other leading image synthesis methodologies, resulting in images of exceptional quality.

The result obtained in this study, which highlights the significant advancement in the generation of synthetic data to strengthen machine learning models, mirrors similar successes achieved by other research conducted during the pandemic period, highlighting a collective interest and progress in the use of synthetic data⁹⁹. The adoption of predictive models based on machine learning, powered by synthetic data, introduces a new era of previously unexplored adaptive and computational capabilities. These technologies not only enhance the prediction and intervention capacity of the healthcare system but also pave the way for personalised medical treatment, raising the standard of care and optimising the allocation of healthcare resources. However, the use of synthetic data is not without its challenges. Appropriate regulation, transparency in the use of data and the accuracy of simulations are critical aspects that require careful consideration. Building a robust regulatory framework and shaping an informed digital culture are essential to effectively integrate synthetic data into digital health, ensuring that technological progress translates into concrete benefits for all citizens.

In conclusion, as Italy's digital healthcare system navigates the complexities of a technological transition and the inherent territorial disparities, synthetic data represents a strategic lever to catalyse change, promising to transform current challenges into opportunities for a more equitable and efficient healthcare future.

⁹⁷ MISCHITELLI, L. (2023, Maggio 16). “Dati sintetici in Sanità: ecco i problemi che possono risolvere”. Agenda Digitale. <https://www.agendadigitale.eu/sanita/dati-sintetici-in-sanita-ecco-i-problemi-che-possono-risolvere/>.

⁹⁸ JIANG, Y., CHEN, H., LOEW, M., & KO, H. (2020). “COVID-19 CT image synthesis with a conditional generative adversarial network” [arXiv:2007.14638].

⁹⁹ DAS, H. P., TRAN, R., SINGH, J., YUE, X., TISON, G., SANGIOVANNI-VINCENTELLI, A., & SPANOS, C. J. (2021). “Conditional synthetic data generation for robust machine learning applications with limited pandemic data”. arXiv preprint arXiv:2109.06486.

4. Legal policy with interpretative and evolutionary proposals

4.1 Synthesis of data in areas other than scientific research

Synthetic data generation is an innovative process by which artificial information is created that retains the fundamental statistical characteristics of the original data. This process plays a key role in a variety of application areas, including but not limited to the financial sector, healthcare, and statistical analysis.

In the corporate context, for instance, the generation of synthetic data serves as a strategic tool for analysing business trends, improving marketing strategies and increasing corporate profitability.

The benefits of data synthesis result in increased efficiency, greater flexibility, and robust privacy protection.

In the financial sector, synthetic data makes a significant contribution to risk assessment and the discovery of new investment opportunities, providing analysts with advanced portfolio management tools.

In fact, the use of such technology is an effective response to pressing needs, both internal and external to organisations. This process overcomes regulatory restrictions on data sharing between different business units, allowing teams to start analysing and working on data before the necessary approvals have been obtained. Furthermore, synthetic data generation proves indispensable in addressing the deficiency of historical data for analysing rare or emerging events. It facilitates the construction of counterfactual scenarios, enabling the testing of strategies and inferences effectively. In addition, numerous studies emphasise the importance of using synthetic data in the financial sector. Among these, the research by Potluru focuses on prototypical applications of synthetic data, exploring how they can revolutionise the management, analysis and sharing of financial data¹⁰⁰.

With regard to the use of synthetic data in areas other than research, the use of synthetic data for statistical purposes should be considered. In this regard, the UK Office for National Statistics (ONS) has explored various scenarios for the use of synthetic data, developing pilot projects, including the preparation for the 2021 Census and the generation of a synthetic version of the Covid Infection Survey, which exploit technologies such as generative adversarial networks (GANs) and differential privacy. These projects aim to test analytical and engineering pipelines, using datasets such as the UK Census and Covid infection surveys to evaluate the effectiveness and safety of using synthetic data¹⁰¹¹⁰².

From improving business strategies to strengthening predictive models in the financial sector and generating statistics for social purposes, synthetic data is proving to be a versatile tool in a variety of scenarios.

¹⁰⁰ POTLURU, V. K., ET AL. (2023). “*Synthetic Data Applications in Finance*”. J.P. Morgan AI Research.

¹⁰¹ Office for National Statistics: Trialling the use of synthetic data at the United Kingdom's national statistics institute - UN GWG on Big Data - Privacy Preserving Techniques Wiki - UN Statistics Wiki. (n.d.).

¹⁰² ONS methodology working paper series number 16 - Synthetic data pilot - Office for National Statistics. (n.d.)

4.2 Opinion 05/2014 on anonymisation techniques (WP 216): why the approach by European authorities should change.

The paper of 10 April 2014 by the Article 29 Working Party, called WP 216, is a landmark paper on personal data protection in the European Union. It offers practical guidance on how to anonymise personal data to ensure that processing activities are in line with European privacy and data protection regulations, including Directive 95/46/EC and the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

Anonymisation is described as a process by which personal data is transformed in such a way that the person to whom it relates cannot be identified. This involves careful design to eliminate any possibility that the data, even indirectly, can be traced back to the original individual.

In addition, the present text clarifies the difference between anonymisation and pseudonymisation. Although pseudonymisation may increase data security by reducing the possibility of a direct link to the identity of the individual, it does not completely eliminate the risk of identification. Unlike anonymisation, which aims to permanently remove any link between the data and the individual, pseudonymisation leaves open the possibility of linking the data back to the individual if additional information is available.

The application of these techniques must be carefully considered, taking into account the specific context, the nature of the data being processed, potential privacy threats and existing technologies. WP 216 emphasises the importance of adopting a dynamic and up-to-date approach to managing data security in response to changes in technology and new modes of attack. Protecting data privacy therefore requires constant efforts to adapt and revise security strategies¹⁰³.

That said, the 'Deloitte' Judgment of the General Court of the Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU), as analysed in section 2.6 above, offers an innovative and potentially transformative interpretation of the distinction between anonymised and pseudonymised data.

In the present case, the Court addressed issues related to the notion of personal data, providing clarification on when a piece of data can be considered anonymous or pseudonymised under the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). According to the GDPR, anonymous data are excluded from its scope, whereas pseudonymised data remain personal data and thus subject to regulation.

The judgment emphasises the importance of assessing the reversibility of the process of anonymisation or pseudonymisation, as well as the availability and use of additional means that could enable the identification of the data subject. This key aspect indicates that the assessment must consider not only the technique used to modify the data, but also the operational context, including the ability to access additional information that could make identification possible.

¹⁰³ Article 29 Working Party (2014, 10 April). Opinion 05/2014 on the processing of personal data in the context of police and judicial cooperation in criminal matters.

In the light of the above considerations, data synthesis as an advanced methodology for generating synthetic data offers further food for thought on the issues of pseudonymisation and anonymisation. In substance, synthetic data generated through advanced synthesising mechanisms, such as those examined in Section 2.7.5 of this analysis, reduce the possibility of re-identification to a sufficiently remote level¹⁰⁴. Therefore, according to WP29 in Opinion 05/2014 WP216, to the extent that data are aggregated to 'a level where individual events are no longer identifiable, the resulting data set can be defined as anonymous'. Thus, even synthetic data generated on the basis of such advanced methodologies could be qualified as anonymous data¹⁰⁵

With the advent and refinement of data synthesis techniques, supported by advanced machine learning capabilities and generative algorithms, numerous data protection methodologies have been developed. Synthesised data represent a promising solution to the challenges of reconciling technological innovation and privacy protection. This technology enables the generation of synthetic data that, while retaining the same statistical characteristics as the original data, does not pose any risk to the identifiability of the individuals from whom such data are derived.

The benefits of using synthetic data are manifold and extend across various domains. In particular, they offer significant advantages in terms of privacy, while at the same time allowing large data sets to be exploited for training machine learning algorithms. This is crucial, for instance, for the medical sector, where the availability of large datasets can accelerate research and development of new treatments and therapies without compromising the confidentiality of patient data.

In conclusion, regulatory and jurisprudential developments in the field of personal data protection underline the importance of adopting a more flexible and innovative approach towards anonymisation and pseudonymisation. In addition, data synthesis is emerging as a promising solution that effectively balances the need for privacy protection with the opportunities offered by advanced data use. Through advanced synthesising techniques, it is possible to overcome the constraints imposed by rigid interpretations, paving the way for new ways of processing data that respect privacy without hampering innovation. This orientation not only aligns data protection law with the challenges posed by technological evolution, but also promotes a data culture that views privacy not as an obstacle, but as an added value in the digital age.

¹⁰⁴ Information Commissioner's Office (ICO). (n.d.). "Chapter 2: How do we ensure anonymisation is effective?" <https://ico.org.uk/media/about-the-ico/documents/4018606/chapter-2-anonymisation-draft.pdf>.

¹⁰⁵ Article 29 Working Party (2014, 10 April). Opinion 05/2014 on the processing of personal data in the context of police and judicial cooperation in criminal matters.

5. Conclusions

5.1 Certification as a tool to ensure synthesiser compliance?

The European certifications, issued under Articles 42 and 43 of the GDPR, which represent a historical novelty in the field of data protection, could offer an effective tool to ensure the compliance of data synthesising techniques as well, promoting the safe and regulated use of synthetic data.

First of all, it should be noted that an approved pan-European certification scheme includes criteria for verifying the conformity of the processing operations performed, which are recognised in several EU and EEA countries, including the respective national supervisory authorities. This extended recognition fosters greater uniformity and trust in the data protection landscape, which could also include the processes of synthesising certified data. As a result, both data controllers (who decide to synthesise their data) and processors (who develop and provide synthesising solutions) can systematically verify the compliance of their processing operations, reducing the risks associated with possible breaches. Furthermore, data subjects can assess the compliance of their service providers, thus ensuring greater transparency. Therefore, the use of the approved criteria of a certification scheme allows compliance with the GDPR to be documented in a structured manner, facilitating the process of auditing and monitoring compliance, including the compliance of synthesis techniques.

Certification simplifies the assessment of compliance and reduces risks for data controllers. It also creates a competitive advantage for data controllers (e.g. synthesis solution providers) whose services are certified, as Article 28 of the GDPR recognises certification as an appropriate tool to validate the technical and organisational measures taken by data controllers. This is particularly relevant for synthesis techniques, which require high standards of security and data protection.

Certification ensures that compliance is not just a formality, but an actual reality, and is recognised as a means of demonstrating data protection by design and by default, as stipulated in Article 25 of the GDPR. Furthermore, in the event of a security incident, such as a personal data breach, the (officially recognised) certification is a mitigating factor in the event of administrative sanctions.

Therefore, the use of certification would be a significant step towards greater security and transparency in the management of personal data. This tool not only facilitates GDPR compliance, but also promotes innovation and competitiveness, offering tangible benefits to all parties involved. In particular, it offers a robust solution to ensure the compliance of synthesis techniques as well, ensuring that these techniques are used in a secure and compliant manner.

5.2 Conclusions: Towards a Secure and Compliant Synthesis of Personal Information

The analysis conducted in this paper demonstrates that data synthesis represents, when implemented through certain methodologies and even certified, an advanced anonymisation technique that complies with current and future data protection regulatory requirements. The evaluation of the individual synthesising technique is necessary to verify how it can be used effectively to generate artificial data that retain the statistical properties of real data, without compromising the privacy of individuals.

In fact, certain synthesis techniques can meet the requirements for anonymisation, described in Recital 26 of the GDPR, which exclude anonymous data from the scope of the regulation, e.g. those based on verifying the distance between real and synthetic *datapoints*, succeed in ensuring that the synthetic data generated do not allow the re-identification of the original data, thus meeting the requirements for anonymisation.

As analysed in the previous paragraphs, guidelines provided by *the Information Commissioner's Office* ('ICO') and European data protection authorities, such as the EDA and EDPS, also encourage the use of 'robust anonymisation' techniques for the protection of personal data.

The use of synthetic data not only preserves privacy, but also enables continuous innovation in the field of artificial intelligence, adapting to the needs of the future regulatory environment outlined by the European legislator.

The European Health Data Space (EHDS) regulation also aims to facilitate access to and sharing of health data by promoting the use of anonymisation techniques to ensure data security. Data synthesis, due to its ability to generate artificial data that retain the statistical properties of the original data, without containing personal information linked to the data subjects, would present itself as an ideal solution to also fulfil the requirements of the EHDS. Generally speaking, the possibility of using synthetic data for scientific research purposes without compromising patient privacy represents a significant advance in health data protection.

Data synthesis thus emerges as a viable *Privacy-Enhancing Technology* ('PET') that complies with both current and future data protection regulations. The advanced synthesising techniques described in this *paper* demonstrate that synthetic data can be generated in a secure manner, preserving the privacy of individuals while ensuring the usefulness of the data for statistical analysis and the training of artificial intelligence models. The capabilities of synthetic data to mitigate re-identification risks are crucial in an era where privacy threats are constantly evolving. The ability to generate data that cannot be traced back to specific individuals offers a robust solution for protecting personal information, while minimising the risks associated with data management and sharing. This is particularly significant in the context of medical research, where the protection of 'sensitive' data is essential to ensure patient trust and information security. Furthermore, data synthesis supports technological innovation, allowing companies and researchers to develop new models and solutions based on high-quality data without compromising the privacy of individuals. This technique facilitates the creation of rich and diverse *datasets* needed for training *machine learning* algorithms and other advanced applications,

overcoming the limitations of real data that may be of low quality or subject to usage restrictions.

In conclusion, data synthesis represents a valuable and strategic solution in the data protection landscape. Its ability to meet regulatory requirements, mitigate re-identification risks and support technological innovation make it a valuable technology for the future of personal data management. As regulations and data protection requirements evolve, synthesis emerges as a useful tool for reconciling the need to protect privacy with the goal of fostering innovation and efficiency in data use.

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